

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

D4.1 New theoretical frameworks

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List of Acronyms

BEF- Biodiversity-Ecosystem Functioning

DOC - Dissolved Organic Carbon

GLV- Generalized Lotka-Volterra

ID- Interaction-Diversity

LBM - Lineage-Based Model

NBSS- Normalized Biomass Size Spectrum

NUM - Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular model framework

PFT- Plankton Functional Types

POM - Particulate Organic Matter

Si - Silicate

Executive summary

A major challenge of marine sciences is to understand how the enormous biodiversity of the ocean has originated and how it is distributed. In addition, during the last thirty years, biodiversity science has become pivotal to understand the functions and services provided by ecosystems. Functions like primary production, carbon sequestration or nutrient cycling largely depend on biodiversity. Understanding the links between biodiversity change and ecosystem functioning is not only relevant for fundamental knowledge, but is also crucial if we aim at predicting the effects of the ongoing biodiversity crisis in the ocean and its effect on society.

This deliverable tackles this challenge and presents new theory and statistical models to better understand and predict marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in the ocean. BIOcean5D has developed multiple new theoretical frameworks that offer a substantial advancement towards better understanding of biodiversity's origin and distribution, how it shapes marine food webs, how it affects the functioning of marine systems, and how biodiversity and ecosystem functioning may respond to ongoing and future disturbances, including climate change.

In particular, this deliverable includes:

- A new model of community assembly that explains why ocean diversity (mostly pelagic) is generated and distributed the way it is. This new model explores the relative role of four fundamental principles in producing global patterns of diversity: the environment, dispersal, population drift and inherited variability.
- A new realistic model of the plankton food web that links nutrients, unicellular and multicellular plankton. The model is publicly available and allows for a better understanding of plankton diversity and functioning and their responses to environmental changes, in particular climate change. Also, by including copepods, which are the basic resources of fish, the model offers a realistic basis for models of fish populations. In addition, we present a new model development that includes gelatinous zooplankton in order to increase even more the realism of plankton food webs.
- A new theory and modeling framework that shows when and how biodiversity is more important for ecosystem functioning, and how biodiversity loss and climate change can alter ecosystem functioning ultimately affecting service provision.
- A new statistical model applied to time-series data of biodiversity-ecosystem functioning relationships (e.g. phytoplankton and primary production) that allows for predicting how important biodiversity and biotic interactions are.

Introduction

In an era when easy access to major databases and computational power is unparalleled in the history of science, one may ask what is the role of theories and models for addressing the many challenges faced by marine sciences. Without adequate theory, we base our knowledge on correlational studies, where causality is unknown, and hence predictive power and forecasting capacity is restricted. This is insufficient to tackle one of the major challenges of ocean research: understanding how the enormous biodiversity of the ocean has originated, how it is distributed and how it is organized within complex food webs. After three decades of intense research, we now know that biodiversity is pivotal to understand the functions and services provided by ecosystems. Functions like primary production, carbon sequestration or nutrient cycling largely depend on biodiversity. Understanding the links between biodiversity change and ecosystem functioning is not only relevant for fundamental knowledge, but also crucial if we aim at predicting the effects of the ongoing biodiversity crisis in the ocean and in society.

In BIOcean5D we have developed **new theories and models to better understand and predict marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in the ocean**. We have developed multiple new theoretical frameworks that offer a substantial advancement towards better understanding of how biodiversity has emerged and is distributed in the ocean, how biodiversity is organized in complex marine ecosystems, how in turn it affects the functioning of marine systems, and how biodiversity and ecosystem functioning may respond to ongoing and future disturbances, including climate change.

This deliverable is structured in five major sections that answer different questions.

The first question is **why marine microbial communities differ across the global ocean?** We have developed a new theory based on community assembly processes (Lineage-based community assembly model LBM in Section 1). Community assembly can be organised around four broad processes: selection, dispersal, drift and speciation. Selection favours organisms whose traits match local environmental conditions. Dispersal moves organisms among locations, potentially connecting distant communities or limiting exchange between them. Drift causes stochastic changes in abundance, especially among rare lineages. Mutation and speciation introduce new lineages into the system. These processes are conceptually distinct, but in natural communities they act together. The model represents phytoplankton as discrete lineages, each composed of an integer number of cells. Lineages undergo stochastic births and deaths, may generate new mutant lineages, experience environmental selection through a simple thermal tolerance trait (Thomas et al. 2012), and are transported through the ocean by a physical transport matrix (Khatiwala et al. 2005). In Section 1 we outline the development of the LBM, demonstrate its behaviour using local and global applications, and show how it can be used to connect large-scale observations of plankton diversity with new theoretical interpretations for community assembly and biogeography.

The second question is **how can we model realistic planktonic communities from basic and universal biological principles?** In Section 2 we provide an answer in terms of the new Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular (NUM) model. The NUM model is a trait-based model

of unicellular and multicellular plankton that uses body size as the main structuring variable for community composition. Its central feature is that body size is used for structuring predator–prey interactions and to scale biological parameters. A distinguishing feature of the NUM model is that the multicellular component, represented by copepods, includes ontogeny, which is crucial in shaping population dynamics. The model encompasses a nutrient pool consisting of nitrogen, silica and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) which interacts dynamically with the plankton community. In Section 2 we present three model setups: a chemostat simulating the photic zone, a water-column, and a global setup. The aim is to provide a user-friendly Fortran-Matlab library which makes the NUM model accessible as a practical tool for marine ecologists or biogeochemical modellers. In Section 3, we present an extension of the model including a **gelatinous zooplankton compartment** that confers even more realism to the model and allows for testing the hypothesis that the inclusion of gelatinous organisms will lead to a more top-heavy community structure compared to a copepod-centric representation alone.

The third question is **when and how biodiversity is important for ecosystem functioning?** The current biodiversity crisis is posing challenges to predicting how ecosystem functions and services will respond to biodiversity change. Yet, most research ignores the most insidious kind of extinction, that of ecological interactions, as formulated by Daniel Janzen over fifty years ago. Now we know that different components of global change profoundly alter biotic interactions in large species interaction networks, yet we ignore how the erosion of these interactions affects ecosystem functioning (Gonzalez et al. 2020). In Section 4 we provide a solution to this in the form of a new predictive theory that integrates network architecture into Biodiversity-Ecosystem Function (BEF) research. The structure of biotic interactions constitutes a missing mechanistic dimension that can explain changes in BEF relationships. Biotic interactions determine how energy and matter flow through ecosystems, shaping both community structure and emergent ecosystem processes. In marine food webs, where trophic links are numerous and dynamic, interaction architecture may strongly modulate the sensitivity of ecosystem functioning to species loss. The theory uses generalized Lotka–Volterra models parameterized with realistic interaction strengths and network connectance values.

Lastly, the fourth question is **how can we determine the importance of biotic interactions for ecosystem functions in observational data?** A large body of work has shown that interactions among microbes can drive ecosystem-level properties such as productivity. However, quantifying the importance of this link is a challenge for remote and highly dynamic pelagic phytoplankton communities, despite their pivotal role in carbon and nutrient cycles. In section 5 we address this gap by applying Diversity-Interaction (DI) models, an approach based on statistical models and mostly used in terrestrial experiments, to a long-term dataset documenting phytoplankton communities in temperate coastal waters (Roscoff-ASTAN, France), combined with a public database of cell sizes. We compared the effects of the presence of pairs of species (“interactions”), size structure of the community, and abiotic effects on the autotrophic total biomass estimated by chlorophyll-a. Section 5 is a proof of concept of how DI models can be applied to other time-series data that are available in the literature, and several generated by BIOcean5D.

1. Lineage-Based Model of community assembly

1.1. Introduction

Explaining why marine microbial communities differ across the global ocean remains a central challenge in marine ecology. Microbial plankton are extraordinarily diverse, and this diversity matters for ocean ecosystem functioning, biogeochemical cycling and the biological response to climate change (Gamfeldt et al. 2015). As the ocean warms, stratifies and changes in circulation, it is increasingly important to understand not only how microbial diversity is structured today, but also how that structure might change in the future (Cavicchioli et al. 2019).

Recent molecular surveys have transformed the scale of this problem. Programmes such as Tara Oceans have revealed immense microbial diversity across the global ocean, generating terabases of metagenomic data from hundreds of samples and identifying tens of millions of non-redundant sequences (Vargas et al. 2015). These data are complex, noisy and incomplete. Accordingly, researchers have not attempted to predict the local abundances of individual taxa and genes, and have instead had success in identifying large-scale macroecological patterns. Across global datasets, plankton communities follow clear rank-abundance distributions (Ser-Giacomi et al. 2018), latitudinal diversity gradients (Sunagawa et al. 2015) and distance-decay relationships in community similarity (Richter et al. 2022). These patterns suggest that marine microbial diversity is structured, but the mechanisms that generate these large-scale patterns remain difficult to isolate.

This difficulty is not unique to marine microbiology. Community ecology has long struggled with the fact that multiple processes can generate similar patterns. As Vellend (2010) argued, community assembly can be organised around four broad processes: selection, dispersal, drift and speciation. Selection favours organisms whose traits match local environmental conditions. Dispersal moves organisms among locations, potentially connecting distant communities or limiting exchange between them. Drift causes stochastic changes in abundance, especially among rare lineages. Mutation and speciation introduce new lineages into the system. These processes are conceptually distinct, but in natural communities they act together.

Global plankton models have traditionally emphasised selection and dispersal (Le Quéré et al. 2005; Follows et al. 2007). In the classical view that "everything is everywhere, but the environment selects" (Baas-Becking 1934; Gamfeldt et al. 2015), ocean currents distribute organisms widely, while local environmental conditions determine which organisms persist. This idea underlies many global models of plankton biogeography, including models in which many discrete populations are transported through a global circulation field and selected by the environment (Dutkiewicz et al. 2020). Other perspectives place greater emphasis on dispersal limitation (Jönsson and Watson 2016) or on stochastic ecological turnover (Ward et al. 2021). Yet these mechanisms are still rarely brought together in a single framework that allows their individual effects to be isolated.

Here we present a Lineage-Based Model (LBM) that aims to achieve this goal. The model represents phytoplankton as discrete lineages, each composed of an integer number of cells. Lineages undergo stochastic births and deaths, may generate new mutant lineages, experience environmental selection through a simple thermal tolerance trait (Thomas et al. 2012), and are transported through the ocean by a physical transport matrix (Khaliwala et al. 2005). Because every lineage is tracked explicitly, the model records where each lineage originated, how old it is, how abundant it becomes, where it is dispersed to and when it goes extinct.

The aim of the LBM is not to reproduce the full complexity of plankton ecosystems. Instead, it provides a theoretical model laboratory for separating the effects of selection, dispersal, drift and speciation on marine microbial community structure. In this report, we outline the development of the LBM, demonstrate its behaviour using local and global applications, and show how it can be used to connect large-scale observations of plankton diversity with new theoretical interpretations for community assembly and biogeography.

1.2. The Lineage-Based Model (LBM)

Most global ocean ecosystem models represent the plankton community as a discrete number of populations (Le Quéré et al. 2005; Yool et al. 2013; Dutkiewicz et al. 2020). These populations may correspond to broad ecological guilds, such as phytoplankton and zooplankton, or to more detailed size classes and plankton functional types. The abundance of each population is usually controlled by environmental factors such as nutrient availability (Monod 1949; Droop 1968), light (Geider et al. 1996) and temperature (Eppley 1972), together with ecological interactions such as zooplankton grazing (Holling 1965) and viral lysis (Suttle 1994). This approach has been successful for representing ecosystem function and biogeochemical cycling (Tagliabue et al. 2016), but it does not typically resolve diversity within each population.

Here we take a different approach. The Lineage-Based Model (LBM) is not a full ecosystem model. It does not attempt to represent feedbacks between populations and the physical or chemical environment. Instead, it represents a single global phytoplankton population regulated by local carrying capacities. This simplification removes much of the ecological complexity of conventional ecosystem models, but allows within-population diversity to be represented in greater detail.

The LBM resolves an arbitrary number of phytoplankton sub-populations (lineages) distributed across a global ocean grid. Each lineage represents a group of clonal cells with no genetic or phenotypic variation within the lineage. Lineages can be rare or abundant, restricted to a single grid cell or spread across the ocean, and can become locally or globally extinct. Because the model tracks each lineage explicitly, it can be used to follow the origin, abundance, age and spatial distribution of diversity through time.

The model is structured around the four mechanisms of community assembly outlined by Vellend : drift, selection, mutation and dispersal. These processes are implemented

separately, allowing their individual and combined effects to be isolated. In the following, we describe how each process is represented in the LBM.

1.2.1. Drift

Drift arises because births and deaths are modelled stochastically. Within each grid cell, individual cells divide and die according to probabilistic birth and death processes. Even when all lineages are ecologically equivalent, random demographic events cause some lineages to increase while others decline. This allows demographic drift to emerge naturally from the individual-level dynamics (Hubbell 2006).

Local population size is regulated by a carrying capacity. In the present implementation, growth declines as total local abundance approaches the carrying capacity. This prevents unlimited local population growth and allows the strength of demographic drift to be controlled by varying local population size.

1.2.2. Selection

Selection can be included by allowing the probability of birth to depend on the match between a lineage's thermal optimum and the local environmental temperature (O'Donnell et al. 2018). Each lineage grows fastest when the environmental temperature is close to its optimum, and more slowly where the mismatch is large. This provides a simple trait-based representation of environmental filtering.

Thermal selection is intentionally simple. It is not intended to describe the full physiology of phytoplankton temperature responses. Instead, it provides a controlled trait axis for asking how environmental selection modifies neutral expectations for lineage loss, turnover and spatial structure.

1.2.3. Mutation

Mutation and speciation are represented by the creation of new lineages from existing ones. During reproduction, some offspring may be assigned to a new lineage rather than remaining in the parental lineage. In neutral simulations, these new lineages are ecologically equivalent to all other lineages and differ only in identity.

In selective simulations, mutant lineages can also inherit modified trait values, such as a changed thermal optimum. Mutation therefore allows the model either to introduce neutral lineage diversity, or to generate new heritable variation on which selection can act.

Figure 1.1. Local processes in the LBM. Each row represents a distinct lineage through time, with hue indicating lineage identity and shading/dot-density indicating abundance. Stochastic births and deaths cause lineage abundances to fluctuate, allowing lineages to increase, decline or go extinct. Dashed circles indicate extinction. Mutations during reproduction create new clonal lineages, shown as branching events from an existing lineage. New lineages may subsequently increase, persist at low abundance or be lost through drift.

1.2.4. Mutation

Dispersal redistributes cells among spatial locations according to the ocean circulation. In the global configuration, passive transport is represented using a physical transport matrix derived from the MITgcm ECCO v4 ocean circulation estimate (Forget et al. 2015). Each column of the matrix represents the spatial probability distribution of plankton cells in one location after dispersal, allowing cells to remain locally or move to other grid cells over one time step.

Dispersal is applied stochastically rather than by multiplying continuous concentrations by the transport matrix. This means that rare lineages can still disperse through low-probability transport pathways. A lineage represented by a single cell has a non-zero probability of being transported elsewhere, allowing the model to track the spatial spread of both rare and abundant lineages.

1.3. Numerical Experiments

The LBM can be run in a range of configurations depending on which of the four community assembly processes are enabled. In this report, we initially test the model within a local (i.e. non-spatial) environment, to better understand how the processes of drift and mutation interact to maintain an equilibrium diversity. We then embed the model within the global framework to examine how dispersal impacts the system response. These simulations are not intended to provide a fully calibrated representation of marine microbial communities. Instead, they are designed to test whether the model behaves as expected in simple limiting cases, and to illustrate how the framework can be used to explore global patterns of community assembly.

1.3.1. Local simulations

We first evaluate the model in a non-spatial configuration. This represents a single local community with fixed carrying capacity and no dispersal. The purpose of this simulation is to illustrate the combined effects of stochastic births and deaths alongside neutral mutation before introducing selection and ocean circulation.

In the local simulation presented here, the community is initialised with 1000 phenotypically identical lineages. Neutral mutations occur during reproduction, creating distinct but still ecologically equivalent lineages. We use this configuration to show how stochastic drift and mutation maintain a predictable diversity of lineages in accordance with neutral theory, as discussed below.

1.3.2. Global simulations

We next embed the local demographic model in the global ocean grid. In this global configuration, each grid cell contains a local phytoplankton population regulated by a carrying capacity, and lineages are transported among grid cells by ocean circulation. This allows initially local lineages to disperse, establish elsewhere, and potentially become widespread.

The global simulations are initialised with a maximally diverse community. For a given carrying capacity, K , each grid cell is initialised with K unique singleton lineages. This makes it possible to track the erosion, persistence and spread of regional community identity through time under different combinations of mutation, drift, dispersal and selection. Lineages can be coloured according to their location of origin, allowing the spatial mixing of communities to be visualised directly.

The LBM allows each of the four community assembly processes to be enabled or disabled independently. In the neutral configuration, all lineages have identical probabilities of birth, death and dispersal, so changes in community composition arise from demographic drift and ocean circulation alone. Mutation can be included to generate new lineages through time, while environmental selection can be introduced by assigning each lineage a thermal optimum and allowing growth to depend on the match between this optimum and the local environmental temperature. This flexibility allows the effects of individual processes, and their interactions, to be isolated and examined systematically.

Global experiments can also be run across a range of carrying capacities. Smaller carrying capacities increase the strength of local demographic drift, causing local diversity to be lost more rapidly. Larger carrying capacities weaken drift, allowing lineages to persist for longer and disperse more widely before extinction. This allows us to examine how the balance between local population size, mutation, dispersal and selection influences the spatial structure of global microbial diversity.

1.4. Results

1.4.1. Local simulations: a mutation-drift balance

We first consider a local community with fixed carrying capacity and no dispersal. The community is initialised with 1000 phenotypically identical lineages and evolves under stochastic births, deaths and neutral mutation. Figure 1.2 shows the resulting trajectory of lineage richness through time.

The community is initialised with substantially more lineages than expected at equilibrium. Consequently, lineage richness initially declines in accordance with a neutral model as stochastic extinction removes lineages faster than new mutations generate them. As richness decreases, the rate of lineage loss slows and the community approaches a mutation–drift balance in which the generation of new lineages is balanced by the stochastic loss of existing lineages.

Once this balance has been reached, lineage richness fluctuates around a stable mean value despite continual turnover of individual lineages. The total number of extant lineages therefore remains approximately constant, even though the identities of those lineages are continually changing. The equilibrium richness is consistent with theoretical expectations and reflects the balance between the introduction of new lineages through mutation and their removal by demographic drift.

Figure 1.2. Lineage richness through time in a local community with fixed carrying capacity and no dispersal. The community is initialised with 1000 phenotypically identical lineages. The dashed line and shaded region show the mean and range across 10 stochastic simulations. The solid black line shows the theoretical decline in lineage richness in the absence of mutation. The horizontal grey line indicates the expected equilibrium richness under neutral mutation–drift balance.

For comparison, the solid black line shows the theoretical decline in lineage richness expected in the absence of mutation. While drift alone would eventually reduce the community to a single surviving lineage, the continual introduction of new lineages prevents this collapse and maintains a stable level of diversity through time.

This result provides a baseline expectation for local lineage diversity in the absence of dispersal and selection. For a given carrying capacity and mutation rate, the model predicts a characteristic local diversity maintained by the continual introduction of new lineages through mutation. Carrying capacity determines the strength of demographic drift, while mutation determines the rate at which new lineages are introduced.

Because mutations arise independently within each community, they provide a continuous source of compositional divergence among locations. In the absence of dispersal, communities would therefore be expected to develop distinct lineage compositions through time, even in the absence of environmental selection. In the spatial model, ocean circulation counteracts this tendency by transporting lineages between locations, increasing similarity among communities and attenuating the differences generated by local mutations. The resulting spatial patterns of diversity will therefore depend on the balance between carrying capacity, mutation and dispersal, while environmental selection may further modify these patterns by favouring lineages whose traits are better matched to local conditions. We explore these ideas in the global model.

1.4.2. Emergence of spatial provinces

Figure 1.3 Emergence of lineage distributions, (a) under ocean circulation and demographic drift and (b) under ocean circulation, demographic drift and selection. Colours indicate lineage identity. Simulations are initialised with 1 lineage with abundance K in each grid cell. Left: $K=100$. Right: $K=100000$.

Figure 1.3a shows the effects of ocean circulation and demographic drift in the absence of mutation and environmental selection. In these simulations, diversity is progressively lost through stochastic fixation while ocean circulation simultaneously transports lineages between locations.

At low carrying capacity ($K=100$), drift is rapid relative to global mixing. Lineages therefore fix locally before they can become widely dispersed. This leads, on intermediate timescales, to the emergence of distinct biogeographic provinces. Once individual regions have fixed to a single lineage, global diversity is subsequently lost through the spatial coalescence of neighbouring provinces, facilitated by ocean circulation. This process continues until a single lineage dominates the global ocean.

At high carrying capacity ($K=105$), drift is much slower and ocean circulation can disperse lineages throughout the ocean before substantial lineage loss occurs. This inhibits the formation of strong spatial structure. Diversity still declines through time, but the ocean remains comparatively homogeneous until a single lineage eventually fixes globally.

Figure 1.3a demonstrates that large-scale biogeographic structure can emerge, at least transiently, from the interaction between dispersal and demographic drift alone, without mutation or environmental selection.

Figure 1.3b shows the corresponding simulation with thermal selection. Lineages are initialised with thermal optima matching the local environment in which they originate. As a result, each lineage is largely restricted to connected regions with similar temperatures, since lineages transported into thermally unsuitable environments are selected against. On ecological timescales (~1 to 10 years), this leads to the emergence of broad biogeographic provinces dominated by a diversity of similar lineages that are all relatively well adapted to the local conditions.

These provinces persist throughout the simulation, reflecting the underlying thermal structure of the environment. Within each province, multiple lineages have similar thermal optima and are therefore nearly neutral with respect to one another. Stochastic drift then reduces this within-province diversity through time, with the rate of loss depending on carrying capacity. At low carrying capacity ($K=100$), within-province diversity is lost rapidly, so each province becomes dominated by a small number of lineages.

The boundaries between provinces are also affected by the carrying capacity. Selection attenuates maladapted lineages as they are transported into new environments, but at high carrying capacity ($K=100000$) larger source populations continually replenish dispersing lineages. These lineages can therefore persist for longer and penetrate further into thermally unsuitable habitats before being lost. As a result, neighbouring provinces have more diffuse boundaries and local communities contain a greater diversity of lineages originating in adjacent regions. Thus, carrying capacity affects both the rate of nearly neutral lineage loss within provinces and the degree of overlap between provinces.

1.4.3. Distance-decay

Figure 1.4 Biological correlation as a function of geographical distance between GRUMP (Global rRNA Universal Metabarcoding of Plankton) surface stations of the AU1603 cruise. a) the empirical 16S GRUMP data, b) the LBM simulation with neutral dynamics and mutation, and c) the LBM simulation with temperature selection of lineages and mutation. Black points represent the pairs of stations and the red dashed line is a linear fit on a linear-log scale of the exponential decay of the correlation. The biological correlation function $g(R)$ measures the degree to which pairs of communities share the same taxa relative to a random expectation.

A common feature of microbial biogeography is the tendency for communities separated by larger geographic distances to become progressively less similar (Richter et al. 2022). This distance–decay relationship emerges from the combined effects of dispersal, selection, mutation and stochastic turnover. Figure~1.4a illustrates this pattern using 16S observations from the GRUMP dataset (McNichol et al. 2025), which show a clear decline in biological correlation with increasing geographic distance.

Figures~1.4b and c compare the observed distance–decay relationship with those generated by the LBM. The neutral model, including mutation, drift and ocean circulation, reproduces a similar rate of decay to that observed in the data, yielding a characteristic correlation length scale close to the empirical estimate. This suggests that mutation, demographic drift and dispersal alone are capable of generating realistic large-scale spatial structure in community composition.

In contrast, the selective model exhibits a much steeper decline in correlation with distance. Communities become decorrelated over substantially shorter distances than observed in the GRUMP dataset, indicating that thermal selection strongly restricts the spatial distributions of lineages. Temperature alone may not adequately represent the ecological niche space occupied by marine microbes. In the neutral model, lineages are able to disperse widely while accumulating diversity through mutation and drift, generating broad-scale spatial correlations. The addition of thermal selection restricts the environments in which lineages can persist, substantially reducing this long-range connectivity. In contrast, real microbial communities are likely structured by multiple niche dimensions, allowing a greater diversity of lineages to coexist and disperse across broad geographic regions.

Overall, the results suggest that mutation, drift and dispersal may be sufficient to explain much of the observed large-scale spatial correlation in microbial diversity, while environmental selection plays an important role in generating persistent biogeographic structure. Modifying the shape of the thermal niche and/or extending the model to include additional ecological niche dimensions may therefore improve agreement with observed patterns of community turnover.

1.5. Conclusions

We have presented a Lineage-Based Model (LBM) for investigating the processes that structure marine microbial diversity across the global ocean. Unlike conventional ecosystem models that represent a fixed number of populations or functional types, the LBM explicitly resolves individual lineages and tracks their birth, death, mutation, dispersal and extinction through time. This framework allows the four fundamental processes of community assembly - selection, dispersal, drift and mutation - to be represented within a single modelling system and examined both individually and in combination.

Local simulations demonstrated that stochastic drift and mutation generate a predictable mutation–drift balance, maintaining a characteristic level of diversity within communities despite continual turnover of individual lineages. Because mutations arise independently within each location, they provide a continual source of compositional divergence that is opposed by dispersal in the spatial model.

Global simulations showed that ocean circulation and demographic drift alone can generate large-scale biogeographic structure. At low carrying capacity, rapid stochastic fixation produces distinct but transient provinces that subsequently coalesce as the ocean circulation mixes them. Introducing environmental selection fundamentally changes this behaviour. Thermal selection generates persistent biogeographic provinces associated with the underlying environmental structure of the ocean, while carrying capacity influences both the

D4.1

loss of nearly neutral lineages within provinces and the degree of overlap between neighbouring provinces.

Comparison with observed distance-decay relationships further demonstrated that mutation, drift and dispersal alone are capable of generating realistic large-scale spatial correlations in community composition. However, the current implementation of thermal selection produces stronger spatial segregation than observed in the empirical data. This suggests that either thermal selection is too restrictive in its present form, or that additional ecological niche dimensions are required to represent the diversity of strategies present in natural microbial communities.

The analyses presented here are intended primarily to introduce the LBM framework and illustrate its behaviour in a number of illustrative cases. Rather than providing a comprehensive evaluation of the model, these examples highlight how the LBM is being applied to assess how mutation, drift, dispersal and selection interact to generate emergent patterns of diversity and biogeography. We are exploring these ideas more systematically in ongoing work. Future publications will provide a more rigorous quantitative analysis of the model's behaviour and its implications for understanding marine microbial community assembly.

Overall, the LBM provides a flexible theoretical laboratory for exploring how local ecological processes interact with global ocean circulation to generate emergent patterns of microbial diversity. The examples presented here demonstrate that mutation, drift, dispersal and selection can each leave distinct signatures in patterns of diversity, spatial structure and community turnover. Future developments should focus on extending the model to include additional trait dimensions and environmental niche axes, allowing a broader range of ecological strategies to emerge. Such extensions will allow the framework to move beyond a conceptual model of community assembly and towards a more mechanistic representation of marine microbial biogeography.

1.6. Code and data availability

The code for the general framework and an actively developed version of the code is also hosted on GitHub at <https://github.com/gkn1r17/DLBM>, where documentation is also available.

2. The Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular modelling framework

The Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular (NUM) model is a trait-based model of unicellular and multicellular plankton that uses body size as the main structuring variable for community composition. The central feature is that body size is used for structuring predator–prey interactions and to scale parameters. For unicellular plankton, trophic strategies across the full range from osmotrophy, phototrophy, phagotrophy, and mixotrophy are an emergent outcome of the model. Another distinguishing feature is that the multicellular component, represented by copepods, includes ontogeny, which is crucial in shaping population dynamics. In addition, the model encompasses a nutrient pool consisting of nitrogen, silica and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) which interacts dynamically with the plankton community.

Here the NUM model is developed to run three model setups: a chemostat simulating the photic zone, a water-column, and a global setup. Here we present a user-friendly Fortran-Matlab library which makes the NUM model accessible as a practical tool for marine ecologists or biogeochemical modellers. The model output is validated with *in situ* and satellite data and demonstrates its applicability in chemostat, water-column, and global setups.

The NUM model framework is fully documented and publicly available on github: <https://github.com/Kenhasteandersen/NUMmodel>, or as a demonstrator of the unicellular component: <http://oceanlife.dtuqua.dk/Plankton/R>.

Figure 2.1. Snapshot of the online NUM model simulator

2.1. Overview

The central problem that ecosystem models face is how to represent the immense diversity of species in a tractable yet mechanistically meaningful way. The dominant approach has been to assemble similar kinds of species into functional groups. In the simplest formulation, the planktonic community is divided into phytoplankton and zooplankton in “NPZ” models

(Franks, 2002). A finer representation of diversity is introduced by subdividing plankton into functional types (Quere et al., 2005) e.g., flagellates, dinoflagellates, ciliates, and diatoms (Butenschön et al., 2016), or into size groups, e.g., small- and large phytoplankton (Neumann, 2000) or sizes of zooplankton (Stock et al., 2014). The addition of each functional group fills another piece in the puzzle towards a complete representation of plankton diversity, however, it also brings a new set of parameters, which must be specified. The expanded set of parameters lends flexibility because the parameters for each functional group can be calibrated to reflect the dominant species in a particular region (Turner et al., 2014). While such calibrations make it possible to achieve good fits with observations, for global applications or for applications of environmental change, where the dominant species may change, the calibration may be driven outside its calibration envelope. Nevertheless, the functional group approach represents a robust solution to the representation of diversity that also retains a direct connection to the taxonomic representation of life.

An alternative approach has been to represent plankton diversity solely through differences in their size (cell size or body size) (e.g. Ward and Follows, 2016; Chakraborty et al., 2020; Andersen and Visser, 2023; Hansen et al., 2024). Using only size to represent diversity eschews any representation of taxonomic diversity, even down to not distinguishing between phyto- and zooplankton. Practically, body size is discretized in a number of size groups with an ordinary differential equation to represent each size group. Although size-based models may well have the same number of state variables as functional-type models, they have only one set of parameters that applies across all groups through scaling relations (Andersen et al., 2016). However, while size is indeed recognized as the “master” trait, pure size-based representations ignore key functional groups such as diatoms (Cadier et al., 2020), bacteria, or obligate phytoplankton and zooplankton. In practice plankton models often adopt a mixture of size-based and functional-group type of models, e.g., using size for diversity inside functional groups of phyto- and/or zooplankton (Banas, 2011; Stock et al., 2014; Ward et al., 2014, 2018), or diatoms (Terseleer et al., 2014). This method enables functional-group type of models to reduce their parameter set through scaling relations with size.

The approach followed here is to represent diversity through functional traits (Kjørboe et al., 2018). In the idealized case, a trait-based approach ignores all taxonomical differences between organisms and only describes differences between organisms through a small set of functional traits (Westoby and Wright, 2006). A trait-based representation of diversity requires a decision about which trait-axes to model, i.e., which traits are most important for the functional diversity of the community. While there is wide agreement about cell or body size as the master trait, various other trait axes have been proposed for the secondary axes, such as investments into resource uptakes: phototrophy and nutrient harvesting (Bruggeman and Bolding, 2014) or including also phagotrophy (Berge et al., 2017; Chakraborty et al., 2017, 2020), degree of gelatinousness (Lemoine et al., 2025), feeding mode (active vs. passive) (Prowe et al., 2019; Serra-Pompei et al., 2020), or vacuolation (Cadier et al., 2020). When traits are discrete, as for active/passive feeding or for unicellular plankton with or without a silicate shell, the trait-based representation becomes essentially identical to the functional type approach. In that respect the differences between the two approaches are

mainly conceptual – whether the representation of diversity is oriented towards taxonomical differences or functional traits.

Here we present an implementation of the trait-based Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular (NUM) plankton model framework (Serra-Pompei et al., 2020). The NUM framework attempts to make a pure trait-based plankton model. It uses cell size as the primary trait for unicellular plankton and silicate shell as a discrete trait (essentially a diatom functional group). For multicellular plankton it uses adult size as the primary trait and active/passive feeding mode as a secondary discrete trait. The NUM framework focuses on the ecology of the plankton and puts less focus on the chemistry. It therefore only includes a very basic representation of nutrient chemistry.

A distinguishing feature of the NUM model is a representation of multicellular plankton which explicitly resolves the developmental stages of copepods. Such representations remain rare (but see Record et al., 2013) for two reasons: first, multicellular zooplankton can increase by several orders of magnitude in body mass from eggs to adults, with a growth rate which depends on the availability of food, among other factors. Representing multiple stages requires several state variables to represent just one species. Second, copepod diversity varies strikingly in different regions (Rombouts et al., 2009) and representing all dominant species in global models is not feasible. The Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular (NUM) model solves the first problem by using an efficient representation of life history as a physiologically structured model (De Roos et al., 2008) and the latter problem by describing the diversity of copepods by two traits: their adult body size and their feeding mode (passive or active) (Serra-Pompei et al., 2020).

A central ambition of the NUM model is to base all parameters on “first principles”, thereby avoiding free parameters that require calibration. The first principles can be related directly to physical laws (diffusion, fluid mechanics, etc.), energetics of chemical reactions, geometry, or mass conservation. This ambition is realized for many of the parameters for the unicellular compartment (Andersen and Visser, 2023). The challenges increase for the multicellular compartment, and here most parameters are determined by cross-species analyses. The description of the parameter values is reported elsewhere (Serra-Pompei et al., 2020; Cadier et al., 2020; Hansen and Visser, 2019; Andersen and Visser, 2023) and the focus here is on the implementation of the NUM framework as a computational platform for plankton ecology on a global scale.

A technical difficulty concerns the reduction of computational time for executing global simulations of full plankton ecosystem models. To provide marine ecologists without expertise in global biogeochemical modelling the ability to perform global simulations we based the global simulations on the transport matrix method (Khatiwala, 2007). The NUM model library version 1.0 is based on the NUM model as described in Serra-Pompei et al. (2022) with a number of key additions: 1) the inclusion of an explicit diatom functional group and silicate dynamics; 2) inclusion of labile dissolved organic carbon and (emergent) heterotrophic bacteria; 3) emergent respiration of unicellular plankton due to uptake regulation; 4) a fast Fortran implementation of the core functions; 5) a matlab front-end

interface with three model setups: chemostat, water column, and global; 6) a flexible configuration of plankton communities, ranging from a single-celled group (e.g. unicellular generalists, including osmotrophs, phototrophs, phagotrophs, and mixotrophs) to a full setup with unicellular generalists, diatoms, sinking particulate organic matter, and a complete representation of the multicellular copepod community.

In the following, we first provide an overview of the NUM model structure and implementation. The full description of equations and parameters are given in Papapostolou et al (2026). Next we show validation and global model simulation results.

2.2. The Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular library version 1.0

Figure 2.2. Conceptual sketch of the NUM framework. Diversity is represented as the cell/organism size (x-axis) in combination with the functional group: unicellular generalists (blue), unicellular diatoms (green), or multicellular copepods or gelatinuous zooplankton.

The core NUM model consists of a set of coupled ordinary differential equations for the state variables. These equations are all coded in a Fortran library for computational efficiency, while the code is executed from a matlab interface. The equations require a representation of the physical environment, which could be a global or regional circulation model or a simple chemostat (Andersen and Visser, 2023). The matlab front-end to the Fortran library interfaces with three environments: a chemostat, a water-column, and the entire globe. All the setups are derived from a global transport matrix that represents a discretized version of the underlying geophysical partial differential transport equations (Figure 2.2). The combination of computationally efficient compiled code with an interpreted language allows to run global simulations on a standard laptop.

The NUM state variables belong to one of three groups: biogeochemical tracers (referred to as “nutrients”, including dissolved organic carbon DOC, nitrogen, and silicate), unicellular plankton (generalists or diatoms), multicellular zooplankton groups (copepods), and particulate organic matter (POM) (Fig. 2.1b). The three nutrient variables are the minimal set needed to represent growth limitation for phytoplankton (incl. diatoms which are limited by silicate) and the carbon source for osmo-heterotrophs (bacteria). The unicellular and multicellular groups are represented by “size spectra” encompassing a number of state

variables that each models the dynamics of one size group (Fig. 2.1a). By implementing several sizes of the unicellular and multicellular groups, the size spectrum of the entire plankton community emerges. Size – defined as cell mass of unicellular organisms and body mass of multicellular organisms – is the key trait that describes resource encounter and uptake, as well as the physiology of individual plankton organisms (metabolism, growth, and reproduction) (Hillebrand et al., 2022). Further, size determines the central process in the model, which is predation by larger organisms on smaller ones (Wirtz, 2012). By using size as the core structuring variable, each organism group is described by one set of parameters defined through size scalings. This approach reduces the overall number of parameters and permits a flexible number of state variables.

The four size spectrum groups described below are generalists, diatoms, copepods, and dead particulate organic matter (POM).

2.2.1. Unicellular generalists

The “generalist” group represents all unicellular plankton including bacteria, phytoplankton, phagotrophs, and mixotrophs (organisms which combine trophic strategies, such as photosynthesis, diffusive uptake of nutrients and predation on smaller cells), but excluding diatoms. This group therefore encompasses a wide range of unicellular organisms, such as heterotrophic and photosynthetic bacteria, flagellates, dinoflagellates, and ciliates, while diatoms are simulated as a separate group (explained in the following section). The generalists are all modeled as potential mixotrophs that acquire carbon and nutrients through a combination of osmotrophy (taking up dissolved organic carbon), autotrophy (photosynthesis), and/or phagotrophy. Whether a given size group represents bacteria, phytoplankton, etc., depends on the principal mode of carbon acquisition, which is determined by a combination of cell size and the environment. The trophic strategies of each size class are therefore an emergent property and vary dynamically over space and time. The generalist spectrum is thus a trait-based model with cell size being the trait.

2.2.2. Diatoms

Large diatoms, which thrive in eutrophic environments, have historically been correlated with food webs that lead to major fisheries (Ryther, 1969). Thus, the inclusion of diatoms in the model is critical for the estimation of fish production potential. Diatoms are simulated as a separate group because of their importance in marine systems (they account for about 40% of marine primary production (Tréguer et al., 2018)), and their distinct characteristics that affect their physiology and predation mortality. Diatoms enclose a vacuole that increases their volume, allowing them to have larger physical size than other cells of the same biomass. In the model, this trait allows them to increase their volume per carbon without additional nutrient demands allowing them to have a higher per-carbon diffusive uptake than non-vacuolated cells. Further, diatoms are engulfed in a silicate shell, which makes silicate another limiting nutrient. The hard silica shell also reduces predation pressure on the diatoms (Hamm et al., 2003; Pančić et al., 2019). The rigidity of the hard silica shell deprives

the cell of the plasticity needed to engulf prey and excludes diatoms from eating prey. Diatoms therefore cannot perform phagotrophy and only obtain nutrients through diffusive uptake. The silicate shell also induces growth limitation of diatoms by dissolved Si, besides light and nitrogen.

2.2.3. Copepods

Multicellular zooplankton are the key link between lower and higher trophic levels, as they ingest unicellular plankton and are themselves prey for fish. Among the different zooplankton taxa in the ocean, copepods are the most abundant metazoans (Humes, 1994). Copepods undergo size changes throughout their life stages and thereby occupy different ecological niches. These ontogenetic niche shifts substantially impact population dynamics (Verity and Smetacek, 1996). For instance, copepod growth rates are strongly correlated with spring bloom intensity (Durbin and Durbin, 1992). To account for these size changes, each population of copepods is represented by a size spectrum that spans from the offspring size to the adult size.

Each population of copepods is characterized by two traits: the adult size and their feeding strategy (active or passive). In this way, the model represents the large differences in adult size observed in the oceans (Brun et al., 2016). Modelling the diversity of copepods with these two main traits makes it possible to represent the entire copepod community in the global ocean with just a few populations that span the trait space of adult size and feeding modes.

2.2.4. Particulate organic matter

Dead organic matter (detritus) is represented by a size spectrum of particulate organic matter (POM) that includes dead organisms, cell fragments from lysis, and fecal pellets produced by multicellular plankton. POM may be represented by a size spectrum to enable the calculation of sinking velocities for different POM sizes. However, in the simulations presented here we simulated just a single size class of POM.

2.3. NUM Model setup and numerical solution

Figure 2.3. Sensitivity of the model to number of unicellular size classes (a–b), number of copepod stages (c–d), and number of copepod groups (e–f). The left column of panels show the Sheldon size distributions (biomass normalized by the width of each size bin; Andersen and Visser (2023, Box V)) and the right column shows total biomass (orange), NPP (green), and HTL production (dark blue) normalized by the value in the standard setup (vertical dashed line). All runs are from a simulation of the water column model at 60°N and 40°W.

The model framework allows for a flexible combination of the four groups. A model setup requires at least one unicellular group (generalists or diatoms) and may include POM and several copepod groups. The default NUM model setup used here involves all four groups. Each group contains several size classes and the model results depend, to some degree, on the number of size classes used in the unicellular groups (Figure 2.3a,b) and in the copepod groups (panels c,d). Further, it depends on the number of active-copepod and passive-copepod groups (panels e,f). The number of size classes and copepod groups in the default NUM model setup is chosen such that the overall results, in terms of size spectra (Figure 2.3a,c,d) and ecosystem function (panel b,d,f), do not change considerably upon the addition of more classes or groups. The setup includes 10 size classes of generalists, 10 size classes of diatoms, two passive copepod groups (adult sizes 0.2 and 5 $\mu\text{g C}$; prosome lengths 320 and 1040 μm), and three active copepod groups (1, 32, and 1000 $\mu\text{g C}$; prosome lengths from 584 and 7200 μm), where each group is discretized in 6 size-classes

representing the growth in body mass. The number of state variables adds up to a total of 54.

Running the NUM model from the matlab interface proceeds in four steps: 1) setting up the simulation type (i.e., choosing which size spectra groups to simulate), 2) setting up the simulation environment (chemostat, water column, or global), 3) running the model, and 4) plotting the output:

```
p = setupNUMmodel( bParallel=true ); % Model setup
p = parametersGlobal( p );          % Model environment
sim = simulateGlobal( p );          % Run simulation
plotSimulation( sim );
```

All parameters are encapsulated in the p structure, which is passed to the simulation (in this example a global simulation). The simulation returns the entire output in the sim structure which is passed on to other functions for analysis or plotting. These two structures are documented on the github site and all functions are documented in their *help* pages.

2.4. Results

Simulations are initiated with concentrations of inorganic nitrogen and silicate from the World Ocean Atlas (Reagan et al., 2023). The simulations presented in the following are after 10 years of simulation with the standard NUM model setup.

We first show the model calibration followed by the model global biomass distributions. We then assess performance with evaluation data, show how the three model environments (global, water column, and chemostat) compare, and finally show outputs related to the physiological dynamics of the organisms in the model.

2.4.1. Model calibration

Figure 2.4. Comparison of model biomass output to in situ calibration data for biomasses of picophytoplankton (a, d), particulate organic carbon (b, e), and copepods (c, f). The top row shows modeled biomasses on the y-axis and observations on the x-axis. The bottom panels show the latitudinal variation of biomasses. Mean biases are -0.70 (a), 0.38 (b), and 0.016 (c), calculated from eq. 21.

The calibration gave an optimal light extinction coefficient of 0.06 m^{-1} , a sinking velocity of 19 m day^{-1} , and a coefficient of higher trophic level mortality of $0.017 \text{ L}(\mu\text{g C day})^{-1}$. The calibrated model produces biomasses of picoplankton, POC, and copepods which are in the correct order of magnitude of the observations (Figure 2.4a–c). Though the three parameters are calibrated to be constant in time and space, the model does produce latitudinal patterns in accordance with the observed patterns (Figure 2.4d–f): elevated biomass at temperate latitudes (-50° and 50°) and around Equatorial upwelling. The modeled copepod biomass approximates observations at temperate latitudes, however, it underestimates copepod biomass in the Equator.

2.4.2. Modeled biomass and productivity

Figure 2.5. Global annual average biomass of (a) generalists, (b) diatoms and (c) copepods. The red star indicates the location (60°N , 40°W) that is used to evaluate the seasonal dynamics in later figures.

Figure 2.6. (a) NUM annual mean NPP, (b) CAFE estimated annual mean NPP (Silsbe et al., 2016), (c) CbPM estimated annual mean NPP (Westberry et al., 2008), (d) VGPM-Standard estimated annual mean NPP (Behrenfeld and Falkowski, 1997), and (e) VGPM-Eppley estimated annual mean NPP. Units are $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$.

The model captures general global-scale biomass patterns, with higher concentrations of unicellular and multicellular plankton in high-latitude seasonal environments and equatorial upwelling areas and the lowest biomasses in oligotrophic gyres (Figure 2.5). These patterns are mirrored in satellite-derived NPP estimates (Figure 2.6). Satellite production of NPP is subject to a systematic bias (Dierssen, 2010), and further the panels b–e highlight the big variation between satellite observation products. Nevertheless, one unrealistic pattern in the model that clearly stands out is the very high biomass and production in the Southern Ocean.

2.4.3. Model evaluation

Figure 2.7. Biomass of nano- ($2\text{--}20\ \mu\text{m}$ radius) and micro-plankton ($20\text{--}200\ \mu\text{m}$ radius) of the model (line) compared to AMT data (markers). a: Transects of the different AMT cruises; b: AMT 12 (May–June); c: AMT 13 (September–October); d: AMT 14 (May). The modeled biomass is the

depth-integrated average of the respective months for each cruise, extracted from the final year of a 10-year global simulation.

Turning to the evaluation data from the Atlantic transects, we see that the model captures the right order of magnitude of nano- and micro-plankton biomasses summed together (Figure 2.7). In these data, increased biomass around equatorial upwelling is less than expected, which is also reproduced by the model. However, the model overestimates plankton biomass at higher latitudes compared to the AMT 14 cruise (panel d), where samples were collected during May. At the global scale, the simulated average macrozooplankton concentration (copepods, larvae, and krill with a prosome length > 2 mm) is of the correct order of magnitude compared to observations, although the correlation is weak.

Figure 2.8. Observed (a) and simulated (b) global surface distribution of the diatom:phytoplankton biomass ratio. Panel c compares the observations and simulations with the color indicating latitude. The observation is a climatological mean from 1998 to 2024 of surface chlorophyll.

The model captures the high surface diatom:phytoplankton ratio in high latitudes but overestimates diatoms in mid latitudes (Figure 2.8). This concurs with observations in the Pacific (Endo et al., 2018) and the Atlantic Oceans (Marañón et al., 2000). The overestimation in mid latitudes could be an artifact of the satellite measurements only seeing the very surface waters, whereas the top layer in the simulations performed here is the upper 50 meter. Further, data from the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey (Reid et al., 2003) shows that diatoms constitute a fraction up to about 50% of the total phytoplankton

biomass throughout the North Atlantic (Barton et al., 2013), in correspondence with the model simulations.

2.4.4. Comparison of environment setups

Figure 2.9. Model output for a 10-year simulation in the global, water column, and chemostat environments at a seasonally stratified location (60°N, 40°W). (a) Total biomass in a water column extracted from the global simulation. (c) Total biomass in the same water column, but extracted from the water-column simulation. (b),(d),(e): Sheldon spectrum of the community from global, water-column, and chemostat simulations at 5 meters depth and geometrically averaged over the last year.

We compared runs of the water-column and seasonal chemostat model setups to the output from a global simulation at a high latitude location (Figure 2.9) that is seasonally stratified. We chose a seasonally stratified location because it exhibits the succession of oligotrophic and eutrophic conditions throughout the year. The seasonal dynamics of total biomass show similar dynamics in the global and water-column simulations (panels a and c): a bloom in spring throughout the water column, followed by a deeper production maximum in summer, and terminated by a smaller autumn bloom. The spring bloom of diatoms is terminated first by silicate limitation, and the generalist bloom is terminated a bit later by nitrogen limitation. Contributing to the demise of the bloom is the grazing by copepods, which become established over summer (panels f–h). The deep maximum is less well represented in the global simulation, with only 13 vertical levels, than the water column simulation with 21 levels.

The size spectra show an overall similar community structure in the global ocean, water column and chemostat simulations (Figure 2.9b,d,e). The plankton biomass is generally higher in the chemostat simulations than in the global and water-column simulations. The physical mixing in the global and water-column models constitutes a loss term by exporting planktonic organisms to the deep water, where they die unless they are mixed back into the

photic zone. In the seasonal chemostat this mixing does not occur. That healthy growing diatoms tend to have near-neutral buoyancy is well established (Gross and Zeuthen, 1948; Smayda, 1970). How they do it is also well established (Boyd and Gradmann, 2002). It is only when cells become stressed (e.g., low nutrients) and die that they start to succumb to gravity (Waite et al., 1992). The modelling assumption that diatoms while growing are neutrally buoyant is relatively robust. The difference in the modelling of mixing losses between chemostat simulations and the two other environments should be kept in mind when using the environments. Nevertheless, the output of the water column illustrates the same dynamics as the global at the same site, indicating that the water column model – which is naturally much faster than a global simulation – performs well. It should be noted, though, that the water column simulations perform best in seasonal environments. In less seasonal environments, the absence of lateral advection appears to result in too low production.

2.5. Conclusion

We have presented a computational library for ecological modelling of plankton communities that resolves their utilization of resources, their trophic strategies, their size-structured population dynamics, and their production of dissolved and particulate organic carbon. The library includes a high-level interface to simulate the communities on global scale, in a water column, or in a chemostat. Because the model includes copepods, which are often weakly represented in biogeochemical models, the model lends itself to linking with fish production models, or to modelling the carbon pump arising from copepod fecal pellets and plankton carcasses. Overall the NUM model is an intermediate-complexity model laboratory for ecological simulations that is accessible to marine ecologists without biogeochemical or physical oceanography background. The focus here has been on the presentation of the general and flexible programming library and the calibration of the core NUM model setup.

The library has been designed with flexibility in mind. It can be run fully from a high-level programming language (mainly matlab). As the core library is written in Fortran, it is straight-forward to implement the model in a full circulation model (Hansen et al., 2024), for example using the FABM interface (Bruggeman and Bolding, 2014). Further, new size-spectrum groups can be added to the library. While POM described here is a single-state variable, the model does include a module to handle POM as an entire size spectrum. A more complex POM module is currently under development (Visser et al., 2024). Future extensions would be the inclusion of an iron nutrient tracer to limit the production in the Southern Ocean, a diazotroph spectrum to include nitrogen fixation, and a description of calcifiers.

Another flexible aspect of the NUM library is the possibility of performing simulations in three environmental settings: global, water column, and chemostat. Water-column or chemostat simulations are useful for making fast model development or trial simulations before moving to full global simulations. However, it should be noted that even though the three settings are

based on the same transport matrix there are differences in the output between them. First, the seasonal variation of total biomass both in the global and water column simulations at a high-latitude location concur: a spring bloom throughout the water column, followed by a deeper plankton biomass maximum in summer (Yasunaka et al., 2021), and a moderate short autumn bloom. However, the global simulation reproduction of the deep maximum is coarser than in the water column, most probably due to a lower vertical resolution. While the structure of the water-column simulations corresponds relatively well with the global simulations in a strongly seasonal environment, they do not match well outside of high-latitude environments, probably due to the absence of advective processes in the water-column simulation. Further, we observe disparity in the size spectra of the community extracted from global, water column, and chemostat models. In particular, the dominance of large diatoms in chemostat simulations, emerges from the absence of mixing losses of plankton in the chemostat simulations, while mixing losses are present in water-column simulations. This finding points to the importance of a better understanding of plankton's ability to maintain a position in the photic zone despite vertical mixing.

Diatoms have been included here as a new size spectrum group. The module is based on an extension of the generalist module with the addition of a vacuole and a silicate shell. In this manner, the diatom module does not use any diatom-specific parameters, apart from the cost of silicate uptake, the size of the vacuole, the minimum and maximum size, and the vulnerability to predation, but shares all other parameters with the generalists. Further, silicate is not incorporated into the POM, it is therefore lost from the model. In light of this very simple description of diatoms, and the important omission of sinking silicate POM, the module performs quite well, as it captures the emergence of large diatoms during spring blooms in seasonal environments and their dominance in high latitudes (Figs. 7b, 14a). Nevertheless, while larger phototrophic diatoms appear in high latitude seasonal regions, they are missing in upwelling regions in the global and water-column simulations (though they do appear in chemostat simulations). The absence of phototrophic diatoms in upwelling regions simulated in the model is implausible, given their known prevalence in such nutrient-rich waters (Benoiston et al., 2017). We conjecture that the absence of large diatoms is due to mixing losses; in nature diatoms are able maintain their position in the water-column by active buoyancy regulation. However, in the global and water-column simulations, diatoms are mixed out. In contrast, the chemostat simulation ignores mixing losses of unicellular plankton. A future fix could be to include buoyancy control in the diatom module to avoid mixing diatoms out and thereby limiting their mortality. Finally, silicate should be included into the POM group. This would require another state variable to account for the variable stoichiometric composition of POM.

2.6. Code and data availability

The code for the general framework and an actively developed version of the code is also hosted on GitHub at <https://github.com/Kenhasteandersen/NUMmodel>, where full documentation is available through the wiki and help pages for all functions (Figure 2.10).

3. Extending NUM with gelatinous zooplankton

3.1. Introduction

The strong influence of the size on the physiology and ecology of organisms have led to the development of a wide range of size-spectrum models (Andersen et al., 2015; Guiet et al., 2016; Blanchard et al., 2017). Size-spectrum models represent the entire marine community as a continuous size distribution and traditionally do not resolve species identity. Their simplicity and parsimonious parameterization make them particularly suitable for investigating human impacts at the community level, including fishing (e.g., Andersen and Pedersen, 2010; Jacobsen et al., 2014; Law et al., 2016), climate change (e.g., Blanchard et al., 2012; Woodworth-Jefcoats et al., 2013; Barange et al., 2014; Dueri et al., 2014), and habitat loss (Rogers et al., 2014).

Traditionally, plankton functional types (PFTs) are used in biogeochemical models to represent plankton diversity. However, this discrete framework does not capture the internal diversity of organisms within each PFT. Model parameters are typically fixed across space and time, implicitly assuming that the same dominant species, with identical physiology and body size, occur across ocean basins and seasons. This assumption is unrealistic, as shown for example by Brun et al. (2016), who demonstrated a clear latitudinal gradient in copepod body size, with smaller individuals predominating near the equator.

In contrast, size-spectrum models explicitly account for the continuous distribution of body sizes within communities, allowing organismal characteristics to emerge dynamically in response to environmental conditions. Even though size-spectrum models do not traditionally resolve species identity, particularly for multicellular organisms, an increasing number of models now include additional traits that influence metabolic rates in ways not captured by body size alone (Serra-Pompei et al., 2020; Heneghan et al., 2020).

In this context, we propose to use the biomass-to-volume ratio alongside body size to improve the representation of zooplankton in size-structured models. Although this trait can be viewed as a continuum, its continuity becomes less apparent when considering total biomass rather than taxonomic occurrence. Within this framework, Kiørboe (2013) suggested that plankton communities are largely dominated by either gelatinous (~0.5% carbon) or non-gelatinous (5–10% carbon) organisms, with relatively few intermediate forms, pointing toward a convergence into two distinct ecological strategies. Here, we represent two non-gelatinous zooplankton groups, as originally implemented in the NUM model (passive and active copepods; Serra-Pompei et al., 2020), alongside a gelatinous zooplankton compartment. We test the hypothesis that the inclusion of gelatinous organisms will lead to a more top-heavy community structure compared to a copepod-centric representation alone.

3.2. Material & methods

3.2.1. The Nutrient-Unicellular-Multicellular size structured model

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The model was composed of four compartments: (i) a size- and trait-structured zooplankton community, (ii) a size-structured community of unicellular protists, a single dissolved nitrogen pool, and (iv) a size-structured pool of fecal pellets. Protists perform photosynthesis, take up nitrogen, and eat other protists. Zooplankton eat protists, other zooplankton, and fecal pellets. The zooplankton community consists of populations of zooplankton characterized by their traits: adult size and biomass-to-volume ratio. For copepods, which refers to zooplankton with a high biomass-to-volume ratio, they are also defined by their feeding mode (passive and active). All processes of protists and zooplankton are described at the individual level, i.e., food encounter, consumption, assimilation, respiration, growth, and reproduction. A full description of the model, equations and parameters can be found in Papapostolou et al., in review.

3.2.2 The multicellular compartment

The energy budget of an individual multicellular organism describes the capture and assimilation of food and how it is allocated to growth and reproduction (Hartvig, Andersen, and Beyer, 2011; Serra-Pompei et al., 2020). Physiological rates scale with body mass and the biomass-to-volume ratio of zooplankton. Most rates used in the model are expressed per unit of carbon mass rather than per individual.

Parameters for copepods were previously defined in Serra-Pompei et al. (2020), and to maintain consistency, we retained all previously established copepods (active and passive feeding mode) parameters. In the following sections, we define the parameters for gelatinous zooplankton and compare them with those of copepods

3.2.3 Feeding process

3.2.3.1 Assimilation efficiency

Assimilation efficiency varies widely depending on feeding conditions, but no clear relationship has been established between assimilation efficiency and body size or biomass-to-volume ratio (Lemoine et al., 2025). Therefore, we assumed the same assimilation efficiency for copepods and gelatinous zooplankton. A value of approximately 2/3 was used as a rough estimate, which falls within observed ranges (Kiørboe, Møhlenberg, and Hamburger, 1985; Lemoine et al., 2025).

3.2.3.2. Preferred predator-prey mass ratio and range

Predator-prey mass ratios for active and passive copepod feeders were previously established by Serra-Pompei et al. (2020), who defined preferred predator-prey mass ratios of $\beta = 10,000$ for active feeders and $\beta = 100$ for passive feeders, following data from Kiørboe (2016). For the preference width (σ), they used values of 1.5 and 1 for active and passive feeders, respectively, allowing for broad preference functions while remaining within realistic ranges (Hansen, Bjørnsen, and Hansen, 1994). Passive-feeding copepods exhibit a narrower preference function than active feeders, as described in Kiørboe (2016).

D4.1

To define predator–prey mass ratios for gelatinous zooplankton, we used data from Lemoine et al. (2025), who established a relationship between predator–prey size ratios and biomass-to-volume ratios.

Predator–prey size ratios were converted into predator–prey mass ratios using the following equation:

$$\text{Predator/prey mass} = \frac{\left(\frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times \left(\frac{\text{length predator}}{2}\right)^3\right) \times dsw \times \frac{\text{CM\%WM}_g}{100}}{\left(\frac{4}{3} \times \pi \times \left(\frac{\text{length prey}}{2}\right)^3\right) \times dsw \times \frac{3}{100}}$$

where length predator and length prey are expressed in centimeters, dsw corresponds to seawater density with a value of 1.025 g/cm³, and CM%WM_g is the biomass-to-volume ratio associated with predator group g. Due to limited information for prey organisms, a biomass-to-volume ratio of 3% was assumed, corresponding to the value observed for most phytoplankton species (Lombard et al., 2024).

The resulting optimal predator–prey mass-ratio equations were then used to define the β parameters. We obtained an exact value of $\beta = 2,185,144$ for gelatinous zooplankton, which was rounded to $\beta = 1,000,000$. For non-gelatinous zooplankton, the exact value obtained was $\beta = 26,072$, which is close to the $\beta = 10,000$ used by Serra-Pompei et al. (2020) for active-feeding copepods, supporting the consistency between the datasets from Kiørboe (2016) and Lemoine et al. (2025).

Finally, the preference width (σ) for gelatinous zooplankton was determined using the maximum and minimum predator–prey mass-ratio equations defined in Lemoine et al. (2025). We obtained $\sigma = 3$ for gelatinous zooplankton and $\sigma = 1.9$ for non-gelatinous zooplankton, values that are also close to those reported by Serra-Pompei et al. (2020).

3.2.3.3 Clearance rate coefficient and exponent

Lemoine et al. (2025) showed that, for the same carbon mass, gelatinous zooplankton exhibit significantly higher clearance rates than non-gelatinous zooplankton. In Serra-Pompei et al. (2020), a clearance rate coefficient of $\alpha F = 0.0052$ was used for passive copepods and $\alpha F = 0.011$ for active copepods.

Using equations for carbon mass–specific clearance rates as a function of biomass-to-volume ratio from Lemoine et al. (2025), we obtained $\alpha F = 0.006$ for non-gelatinous organisms, which is very close to the values reported for passive copepods, and $\alpha F = 0.1141$ for gelatinous zooplankton.

An exponent of 0.75 was retained for all three zooplankton populations, as metabolic theory predicts that most metabolic rates scale with body mass following a 3/4 power law.

3.2.3.4 Maximum ingestion rate coefficient and exponent

For copepods, Serra-Pompei et al. (2020) defined a maximum ingestion rate coefficient of 0.4 for passive copepods and 1.37 for active copepods, based on Kiørboe and Hirst (2014).

Using the same dataset, we did not find a significant difference between the maximum ingestion rates of gelatinous and non-gelatinous zooplankton.

Therefore, we used the same maximum ingestion rate as for passive copepods (0.4), as gelatinous zooplankton appear to fall within the lower range of maximum ingestion rates observed for non-gelatinous zooplankton.

An exponent of 0.75 was retained for all three zooplankton groups, as metabolic theory predicts that most metabolic rates scale with body mass following a 3/4 power law.

3.2.4 Reproduction process

3.2.4.1 Reproductive efficiency

Reproductive efficiency for copepods accounts for the ratio of males to females and the survival of eggs until hatching. To estimate egg survival, Serra-Pompei et al. (2020) used egg mortality rates and hatching times from Kiørboe and Sabatini (1994), obtaining a value of 0.5 for both feeding modes. Assuming a 1:1 male-to-female ratio, the overall reproductive efficiency is therefore $r = 0.25$.

However, gelatinous taxa encompass a wide diversity of life cycles, including alternation between sexual and asexual reproduction (e.g., salps), as well as the presence of benthic life stages in some groups (e.g., medusae). Due to the lack of data and the complexity of reproductive strategies in these groups, we retained the same reproductive efficiency values as those used for copepods for gelatinous zooplankton.

3.2.4.2 Adult offspring

Copepods produce offspring whose size is proportional to adult body size. The adult-to-egg mass ratio varies from 100 to 1000 and differs between broadcast spawners and sac-spawners (Kiørboe and Sabatini, 1995; Neuheimer et al., 2015). For simplicity, Serra-Pompei et al. (2020) assumed an adult-to-offspring ratio of 100 between adults and the first nauplius stage.

For gelatinous zooplankton, we compiled data on adult and offspring sizes for ctenophores (Neuheimer et al., 2016), larvaceans (Lombard et al., 2009), salps (Heron et al., 1972), and cnidarians (Mercier et al., 2016; Neuheimer et al., 2016). We did not find systematic differences in the adult-to-offspring ratio between copepods and gelatinous organisms. Therefore, we retained an adult-to-offspring ratio of 100 for gelatinous zooplankton.

3.2.5 Respiration process

Measured respiration rates represent total organismal respiration, including basal metabolic costs and activity-related expenditures such as specific dynamic action and swimming. To define copepod respiration rates, Serra-Pompei et al. (2020) used data from Kiørboe and Hirst (2014), which were standardized to a reference temperature of 15°C.

However, in Lemoine et al. (2025), no strong difference was found in respiration rates between gelatinous and non-gelatinous zooplankton for a given carbon mass. Therefore, we used the same respiration rate values for all zooplankton populations.

3.2.6 Mortality rate

As zooplankton represent the highest trophic levels explicitly resolved in the model, they are not subject to explicit predation. Therefore, mortality parameters representing predation by higher trophic levels were introduced to account for their losses. Gelatinous zooplankton experience mortality rates one order of magnitude higher than non-gelatinous zooplankton. Owing to the lack of precise experimental constraints, we therefore imposed a mortality rate for gelatinous organisms ten times higher than that of copepods.

3.3. Results

Figure 3.1: Proportion of zooplankton across a chlorophyll a gradient

The proportion of gelatinous organisms decreased with increasing chlorophyll *a* concentration (Figure 3.1), declining from nearly 40% of total zooplankton biomass at 0.03 mg Chl-*a* m⁻³ to approximately 5% at 3 mg Chl-*a* m⁻³. In contrast, the proportion of total copepods increased with chlorophyll concentration, rising from about 60% of total zooplankton biomass in oligotrophic regions to nearly 95% in more productive environments. Within the copepod community, active copepods increased in relative biomass with increasing chlorophyll concentration, whereas passive copepods declined. However, the decrease in passive copepods was less pronounced than for gelatinous zooplankton, decreasing from approximately 20% of total zooplankton biomass in oligotrophic regions to around 15% in more productive environments.

3.3.1. Marine ecosystem structure

Figure 3.2.: Normalized Biomass Size Spectrum, NBSS slope (S_{NBSS}) distribution.

Comparison of S_{NBSS} between two model configurations: (i) NUM copepod-only (green), and (ii) NUM copepod + gelatinous zooplankton (blue), together with observed S_{NBSS} from Lombard et al. (2024) based on the Tara Oceans expeditions (purple). (a) Model outputs resampled at the same sampling locations as the Tara Oceans observations. (b) Global model outputs used to compute S_{NBSS} distributions.

We compared the trophic slope distribution derived from the observational dataset with those predicted by the two versions of the model: (i) the version in which the multicellular compartment is composed only of non-gelatinous zooplankton (“NUM copepod only”), and (ii) the version including both gelatinous and non-gelatinous zooplankton (“NUM copepods & gelatinous”). We then compared two different sampling approaches: one in which model outputs were resampled at the observation stations to ensure a more consistent comparison between observations and simulations, and another using the complete global model outputs (Figure 3.2).

The trophic slope distribution from the observational dataset is characterized by 63% of values being greater than -1 , indicating a predominance of “top-heavy” inverted trophic pyramids in the observational data. For the resampled model outputs, the NUM copepod-only version shows a majority of trophic slopes below -1 , with 63% of the slopes corresponding to “bottom-heavy” trophic pyramids. In contrast, the inclusion of gelatinous zooplankton reverses this pattern: in the resampled outputs, 78% of the slopes are greater than -1 , indicating a predominance of “top-heavy” inverted pyramids. This new version therefore shows much better agreement with the observational data.

Nevertheless, the global model outputs exhibit slightly different results. The copepod-only version displays an even stronger dominance of “bottom-heavy” interactions than the

resampled outputs, with 76% of slopes below -1 . For the version including both gelatinous zooplankton and copepods, a markedly different distribution is observed, with a nearly balanced repartition between bottom-heavy (54%) and top-heavy (45%) trophic pyramids.

Figure 3.3. Global distribution of the NBSS slope predicted by the NUM copepod & gelatinous model. The NBSS slope is related to the balance between consumers and prey and is used here as a proxy for the slope of the trophic pyramid. NBSS slopes < -1 (shown in blue) are assumed to represent conventional “bottom-heavy” trophic pyramids, whereas flatter slopes (> -1) are associated with “top-heavy” inverted trophic pyramids (shown in red). Black dots indicate the sampling locations of the Tara Oceans Expedition stations corresponding to the observational dataset.

3.4. Discussion

In this study, we implement a new multicellular population representing gelatinous zooplankton. To parameterize this population, we adopt a trait-based approach, using the biomass-to-volume ratio as a key descriptor to distinguish gelatinous organisms from non-gelatinous ones such as copepods. In particular, we test the hypothesis that gelatinous zooplankton experience mortality rates one order of magnitude higher than those of non-gelatinous zooplankton. We perform two simulations: (i) one using identical mortality rates for both zooplankton groups, and (ii) one using a mortality rate ten times higher for gelatinous zooplankton than for copepods.

Using identical mortality rates leads to an unrealistic dominance of gelatinous zooplankton and even to a strong gelatinous-driven top-down control of copepods, as copepod biomass strongly decreases with increasing gelatinous biomass. By contrast, imposing a mortality rate ten times higher for gelatinous organisms, together with parameter values derived from the biomass-to-volume ratio (Lemoine et al., 2025), allows us to obtain a total biomass distribution between gelatinous and non-gelatinous zooplankton that is consistent with in situ estimates from Clerc et al. (in prep.). Furthermore, the copepod parameters used in Serra-Pompei et al. (2020), which were specifically calibrated for active and passive copepods, are very close to those that can be derived using the trait-based approach with a carbon-to-wet-mass ratio of 9%, corresponding to the average value observed for copepods

(McConville et al., 2017). These results therefore strongly suggest that the use of the biomass-to-volume ratio as a guiding trait for zooplankton parameterization can provide a realistic representation of zooplankton biomass within the model. More broadly, this approach could help future ecosystem models incorporate greater zooplankton diversity while constraining parameter values in a biologically consistent framework.

Gelatinous organisms promote the emergence of top-heavy planktonic structures.

We compared the marine ecosystem structure predicted by the two versions of the model (copepod-only and copepod + gelatinous) with the observational dataset. For both the station-resampled outputs and the global model outputs, the inclusion of gelatinous zooplankton leads to an increase in the proportion of top-heavy trophic pyramids compared to the copepod-only version. These results reinforce those of Lombard et al. (2024, preprint), who showed that in situ data indicate that 55% of top-heavy planktonic ecosystems are dominated by gelatinous organisms.

Several mechanisms linked to specific biological and ecosystem properties have been proposed to favour the emergence of top-heavy trophic structures (McCauley et al., 2018). For instance, top-heavy ecosystems are expected to emerge when there is increased transfer efficiency across trophic levels, such as through enhanced foraging efficiency of consumers (Jennings et al., 2007). The physiology of gelatinous zooplankton may contribute to increasing the overall foraging efficiency within zooplankton communities, as studies have highlighted higher clearance rates for gelatinous organisms compared to non-gelatinous zooplankton (Acuña et al., 2011; Lemoine et al., 2025). In addition, an increase in the size of higher trophic level organisms relative to lower trophic levels has been identified as a mechanism promoting the emergence of top-heavy patterns (Jennings et al., 2007; Barnes et al., 2010; Jonsson, 2017). Gelatinous zooplankton fit this framework due to their extremely low biomass-to-volume ratios, allowing them to reach very large sizes while still preying on much smaller organisms. This results in a significantly higher predator–prey size ratio compared to non-gelatinous organisms (Lemoine et al., 2025).

Finally, the behavioural ecology of consumers within a given community can also regulate trophic pyramid structure, particularly through foraging strategies. Omnivores feeding across multiple trophic levels or on a broad range of prey are thought to more efficiently channel energy through food webs (Shurin et al., 2006; deBruyn et al., 2007). This occurs because they can bypass inefficient feeding pathways and draw energy from multiple resource pools within the ecosystem (Utne-Palm et al., 2010; McCauley et al., 2018). This mechanism is also relevant for gelatinous filter-feeding organisms, which exhibit a broader prey-size spectrum than non-gelatinous zooplankton (Lemoine et al., 2025) and therefore a high capacity to integrate energy across trophic levels. Overall, our results further highlight the capacity of gelatinous organisms to promote the emergence of top-heavy planktonic structures.

4. Biotic interactions as a unifying framework for scaling-up Biodiversity-Ecosystem Function

4.1. Summary

Understanding how biodiversity loss alters ecosystem functioning remains a central challenge in ecology. Although numerous studies show that ecosystem processes such as biomass accumulation or carbon fixation increase with species richness, the magnitude of this effect varies substantially across systems and scales. As stated in the document, “the slope of this relationship varies significantly across systems; scales of observation, and levels of biological complexity” (Cardinale et al., 2012; Gonzalez et al., 2020). Identifying the mechanisms behind this variability is essential for predicting ecosystem responses under global change.

Marine ecosystems provide a particularly relevant context for advancing Biodiversity–Ecosystem Function (BEF) theory. Classical BEF research has been developed primarily in terrestrial plant communities, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding how these relationships operate in the ocean (Hooper et al., 2005; Stachowicz et al., 2007). Marine systems differ markedly from terrestrial ones: they exhibit higher physical connectivity, strong size-structuring, and rapid nutrient and biomass turnover driven by phytoplankton (Shurin et al., 2006; Steele et al., 2019). As the document notes, “marine production is frequently driven by phytoplankton communities with high turnover rates, which can fundamentally alter the BEF slope” (Beaugrand et al., 2010). These characteristics suggest that the processes linking biodiversity to ecosystem functioning in marine environments may differ from those observed on land.

A persistent discrepancy in BEF research is the contrast between experimental and observational findings. Controlled experiments typically reveal strong positive BEF relationships, whereas field studies often detect weaker or more variable effects (Duffy et al., 2017; Gonzalez et al., 2020). While environmental heterogeneity and scaling effects have been proposed as explanations, these factors alone do not fully account for the observed patterns.

In this research, we propose that the structure of biotic interactions constitutes a missing mechanistic dimension that can reconcile these inconsistencies. Biotic interactions determine how energy and matter flow through ecosystems, shaping both community structure and emergent ecosystem processes. In marine food webs, where trophic links are numerous and dynamic, interaction architecture may strongly modulate the sensitivity of ecosystem functioning to species loss.

As part of this deliverable, we present the theoretical framework that explicitly integrates trophic network structure into BEF scaling. Using generalized Lotka–Volterra models parameterized with realistic interaction strengths and connectance levels, we show that variation in interaction architecture systematically alters BEF slopes. Sparse or weakly interacting networks tend to exhibit steep BEF relationships, indicating high vulnerability to

species loss. In contrast, highly connected or strongly interacting networks display shallower slopes, reflecting greater functional redundancy and resilience.

This interaction-based perspective provides a unifying explanation for the diversity of BEF patterns observed across ecosystems. It also offers a mechanistic foundation for predicting how global change drivers—such as habitat fragmentation, warming, or altered trophic efficiencies—reshape BEF relationships by modifying the underlying interaction network. By placing biotic interactions at the core of BEF theory, this framework enhances our capacity to scale up biodiversity effects from controlled experiments to real-world ecosystems, particularly in the ocean where trophic dynamics dominate ecosystem functioning.

Figure 4.1: Conceptual representation of how biodiversity influences ecosystem functioning through trophic interactions. The figure illustrates how initial species richness affects ecosystem functioning, measured here as total biomass. The left panels show multiple model realizations generated from randomly sampled interaction matrices, representing variability in trophic structure under fixed parameters. Each interaction matrix defines a trophic network (top-centre panel) that determines energy and biomass flows. The lower panel displays a representative Generalized Lotka–Volterra (GLV) simulation for a three-species network, showing biomass dynamics over time. Aggregating simulations across richness levels produces the biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) relationship shown on the right.

4.2. Methods

4.2.1. Generalized Lotka–Volterra (GLV) Model

We used a standard Generalized Lotka–Volterra (GLV) model to explore the effects of biotic interactions on the biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) relationship. The GLV framework is widely used to model the dynamics of ecological communities, capturing key features of species interactions and their nonlinear effects on community structure and function (Allesina & Tang, 2012; Barabás et al., 2017).

The GLV model is described by a set of ordinary differential equations governing the growth of each species as a function of its interactions with other species:

$$\frac{d\vec{N}}{dt} = \vec{N} \odot (\vec{r} + A\vec{N}),$$

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = r_i N_i + \sum_{j=1}^S a_{ij} N_j N_i,$$

where N_i is the biomass (or abundance) of species i , r_i is its intrinsic growth rate, and a_{ij} represents the per-capita effect of species j on species i . The summation runs over all species in the community (with S denoting the total species richness). Interaction strengths a_{ij} may be positive (facilitative or mutualistic) or negative (competitive or trophic). In this study, we explicitly focus on trophic interactions within food webs; therefore, if $a_{ij} > 0$ (representing a functional benefit to predator i from prey j), the reciprocal interaction matrix coefficient strictly satisfies $a_{ji} < 0$.

4.2.2. Maximum Interaction Strength

Both core structural axes of our study—interaction strength and network connectance—are structurally implemented via the community interaction matrix A . Self-regulation terms populate the main diagonal and are initialized symmetrically for all species in the pool:

$$a_{ii} = \alpha = 0.1$$

Off-diagonal elements are stochastically sampled from a continuous uniform distribution and subsequently scaled to explicitly define the maximum interaction strength baseline ω :

$$a_{ij} = U(-1, 1) \times \omega$$

Trophic structural constraints are enforced across the network by establishing directional reciprocal predator–prey interactions:

$$a_{ij} = -\phi \times a_{ji}$$

where ϕ represents the metabolic biomass transfer efficiency factor. Consequently, directional predator mass gains are bounded to be smaller in absolute magnitude than the corresponding prey population losses. The comprehensive finalized interaction matrix can be formalized as:

$$A = \alpha I + \omega U$$

where I is the identity matrix and U contains the signed, scaled off-diagonal interaction terms consistent with the dictated predator–prey configuration matrix topology.

4.2.3. Network Connectance and Pruning Protocol

To systematically vary network connectance parameters independent of species pool size (S^2), we implemented a customized Monte Carlo pruning procedure. For each potential interacting species pair (a_{ij}, a_{ji}) , the probability of retaining an active trophic link is calculated based on the target expected mean degree of the web (k):

$$P(\text{edge kept}) = \frac{k}{N-1}$$

where k represents the target expected mean degree of the web. For each interaction pair, a random value was drawn from a uniform distribution: $r \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$; if $r < k / (N - 1)$, the interaction coefficients were successfully retained. Otherwise, both reciprocal matrix entries were truncated to zero.

To prevent the artifactual generation of completely isolated nodes, this stochastically driven sampling loop was iteratively repeated until every single species node achieved an in-degree or out-degree ≥ 1 . This ensures a fully integrated food web structure where no species is decoupled from the community.

4.2.4. Growth Rate Assignment

Intrinsic growth rates were non-randomly assigned according to discrete trophic positions. Following matrix structure construction, primary autotrophs were uniquely identified as network nodes possessing an in-degree of exactly zero. These basal nodes were assigned a positive intrinsic vegetative growth rate γ_A , whereas consumer heterotrophs received a significantly lower corresponding baseline growth rate γ_H .

Figure 4.2: Examples of ecosystem structures generated across gradients of network connectance and interaction strength. The figure illustrates representative trophic network configurations obtained by varying two key structural parameters: network connectance (vertical axis) and maximum interaction strength (horizontal axis). Increasing connectance produces denser networks with more consumer–resource links, whereas increasing interaction strength intensifies trophic regulation. Together, these gradients

generate a wide range of ecosystem architectures used to evaluate how biotic interactions influence biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationships.

4.2.5. Growth Rate Assignment

To comprehensively evaluate emergent multi-trophic ecosystem functioning within this GLV framework, we quantified two independent primary macro-ecological metrics from our finalized long-term numerical simulations: cumulative biomass pools and dynamic biomass flow.

The first metric captures the long-term aggregate biomass accumulated within the system. We integrated the GLV differential equations over a sufficiently long time horizon to ensure the system reached its stable asymptotic dynamics. To account for potential non-equilibrium behavior, such as limit cycles or chaotic attractors, and eliminate transient variations, we computed the time-averaged abundance vector $\langle N \rangle$ over an extended post-convergence window. From these persistent abundances, we calculated the total system biomass and further partitioned it into two distinct functional groups based on the network's trophic topology:

Resource Biomass: The aggregate time-averaged equilibrium biomass of autotrophs (basal species), structurally defined as network nodes with a quantified in-degree of zero ($k_{in} = 0$).

Consumer Biomass: The aggregate time-averaged equilibrium biomass of heterotrophs, structurally defined as consumer species that trophically exploit at least one other species node in the network ($k_{in} \geq 1$).

The second metric, biomass flow, quantifies the operational energy flux across the food web by measuring the total volume of biomass transferred between trophic links during the final time step of the simulation (T). This dynamic flow is a function of the instantaneous abundance vector $N(T)$ and the predation coefficients. To isolate directed energy propagation and exclusively capture the biomass successfully incorporated by consumers, we restrict our calculation to positive interaction rates where $a_{ij} > 0$ (representing the benefit to predator i from prey j). Mathematically, the total system-wide biomass flow (F) at the final simulation step is computed as:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^S \sum_{j \neq i}^S a_{ij} N_i(T) N_j(T), \quad \text{for } a_{ij} > 0.$$

4.3. Results

As part of this deliverable, we quantified how biotic interaction architecture—specifically network connectance and interaction strength—modulates the biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) relationship in multi-trophic systems. Using ensembles of generalized Lotka–Volterra (GLV) trophic networks, we systematically varied the density of trophic links and the magnitude of interaction strengths to disentangle the direct effects of species richness from the structural properties of ecological networks. Across thousands of simulated communities, we evaluated total ecosystem biomass, biomass flow, and the distribution of biomass across trophic levels.

Figure 4.3: Network connectance and interaction strength modulate the sensitivity of ecosystem functioning to biodiversity loss. (a) Increasing network connectance (mean degree, k) reduces BEF slopes, indicating that highly connected networks are less sensitive to species loss. (b) Increasing interaction strength produces a similar effect, with strong interactions weakening the dependence of ecosystem functioning on species richness. Insets show representative BEF relationships for selected parameter combinations. In panel (a), maximum interaction strength is fixed at 0.5; in panel (b), mean degree is fixed at 1.

4.3.1. Effects of network connectance on ecosystem functioning

Increasing network connectance consistently reduced BEF slopes (Figure 4.3). Highly connected networks showed shallow BEF relationships, indicating that ecosystem functioning was less sensitive to species loss. In contrast, sparsely connected networks exhibited steep BEF slopes, meaning that small reductions in species richness produced large declines in total biomass.

This pattern arises because low-connectance networks allow species to reach high equilibrium biomasses, making individual species disproportionately important for ecosystem functioning. In highly connected networks, trophic interactions distribute biomass across many consumer–resource pathways, increasing functional redundancy and buffering the system against extinctions. These dynamics are consistent with the simulations shown in Figure 4.2, where connectance determines the range of possible trophic architectures.

4.3.2. Effects of interaction strength on BEF slopes

Weak interaction strengths produced similar qualitative effects to low connectance but with more abrupt transitions. Networks dominated by weak interactions accumulated higher total biomass but were more sensitive to species loss, resulting in steep BEF slopes. As interaction strength increased, BEF slopes remained high until reaching a threshold beyond which they declined sharply.

This behaviour reflects the shift from dynamics dominated by intrinsic growth rates (weak interactions) to dynamics dominated by trophic regulation (strong interactions). Strong interactions constrain biomass accumulation and reduce the marginal contribution of individual species, increasing resilience to biodiversity loss.

4.3.3. Combined effects of connectance and interaction strength

The joint parameter space of connectance and interaction strength (Figure 4.4) reveals that BEF slopes are lowest in networks that are both highly connected and strongly interacting. These systems exhibit high trophic overlap and redundancy, making ecosystem functioning robust to species loss. Conversely, sparse networks with weak or moderate interaction strengths show the steepest BEF slopes and the highest vulnerability.

Across the parameter space, changes in connectance generally produced larger shifts in BEF slopes than equivalent changes in interaction strength. However, in networks with low connectance and strong interactions—such as host–parasitoid systems—small changes in interaction strength produced disproportionately large effects on BEF slopes, consistent with empirical observations.

Figure 4.4: Influence of trophic network structure on the biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationship. The figure shows how BEF slopes vary across gradients of network connectance and interaction strength. Increasing either the number of interactions per species or the strength of those interactions consistently reduces BEF slopes, indicating lower sensitivity of ecosystem functioning to species loss. When interactions are weak and networks are sparsely connected (bottom-left region), ecosystem functioning is dominated by autotrophs and declines sharply with species loss. In contrast, highly connected networks with strong interactions (top-right region) provide multiple alternative pathways for energy and matter flow, resulting in greater functional redundancy and weaker BEF coupling.

4.3.4. Influence of metabolic constraints

To assess the generality of these patterns, we evaluated how metabolic parameters modify BEF relationships (Figure 4.5). Varying self-regulation coefficients altered the absolute magnitude of ecosystem biomass but did not change the qualitative dependence of BEF

slopes on trophic architecture. Increasing the metabolic disparity between autotrophs and heterotrophs reduced overall BEF slopes but preserved the same structural gradient.

Relaxing the assumption of perfect trophic antisymmetry—introducing trophic inefficiency—reduced total biomass but did not alter the position of minimum or maximum BEF slopes. This confirms that interaction architecture, rather than metabolic detail, is the primary determinant of BEF sensitivity.

Figure 4.5: Influence of trophic efficiency and growth-rate asymmetries on BEF slopes. The figure shows how variation in trophic efficiency and differences between autotroph and heterotroph growth rates affect biodiversity–ecosystem functioning (BEF) slopes. Although these parameters modify specific combinations of biotic interaction strengths and connectance, the qualitative pattern remains consistent: increasing the influence of biotic interactions leads to shallower BEF slopes. White contour lines indicate changes of 0.1 in BEF slope to facilitate comparison across parameter combinations. This pattern is robust across the GLV model variants tested, including scenarios where heterotrophs incur a metabolic cost (negative intrinsic growth rate, rightmost column), confirming that further specification of the model does not alter the general decline in BEF slope.

4.3.5. BEF relationships across multiple ecosystem functions

We extended the analysis beyond total biomass to evaluate producer biomass, consumer biomass, and biomass flow (see figure 4.6). All functions showed the same qualitative dependence on connectance and interaction strength as total biomass. However, the location of maximum BEF slopes differed across functions:

- Producer biomass peaked at low connectance
- Consumer biomass peaked at intermediate connectance and interaction strength
- Biomass flow aligned with consumer biomass

Despite these differences, the overall functional landscape remained consistent: interaction erosion increases BEF slopes across all ecosystem functions, confirming that trophic architecture is the primary determinant of BEF sensitivity.

Figure 4.6: Trophic network architecture consistently constrains multiple ecosystem functioning metrics. (a) Schematic representation of the simulated multitrophic networks. (b–e) BEF slopes for biomass flow (b), total biomass (c), producer biomass (d), and consumer biomass (e) across the parameter space of connectance and interaction strength. High BEF slopes consistently occur in low-connectance networks with weak to intermediate interaction strengths, demonstrating that interaction architecture shapes ecosystem functioning across all metrics.

4.3.6. Implications for understanding the consequences of global change

Global change drivers modify BEF relationships by altering biotic interactions. Habitat loss reduces connectance more rapidly than species richness, shifting ecosystems toward regions of steep BEF slopes and increasing vulnerability. Warming generally increases interaction strength, moving ecosystems toward shallower BEF slopes and partially buffering functional responses to species loss. When both drivers act simultaneously, their effects partially counterbalance, producing intermediate BEF slopes (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7: Effects of global change drivers on the biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationship. The figure illustrates how changes in biotic interactions modify ecosystem resilience to species loss. Variation in BEF slopes across the interaction-parameter space reflects differences in functional buffering: shallow slopes indicate low sensitivity of ecosystem functioning to biodiversity loss, whereas steep slopes indicate reduced resilience. (a) Reduced network connectance, as expected under habitat loss or fragmentation, increases BEF slopes and makes ecosystem functioning more dependent on species richness. (b) Increased interaction strength, such as under warming, reduces total biomass and constrains species abundances, resulting in weaker BEF coupling. (c) When both drivers act simultaneously, their effects partially counterbalance, producing intermediate variations of BEF slopes.

5. Statistical model to disentangle the role of diversity and interactions for ecosystem functioning in remote systems.

5.1. Summary

A large body of work has shown that interactions among microbes can drive ecosystem-level properties such as productivity. However, quantifying the importance of this link is a challenge for remote and highly dynamic pelagic phytoplankton communities, despite their pivotal role in carbon and nutrient cycles.

To address this gap, we applied Diversity-Interaction (DI) models, an approach based on statistical models and mostly used in terrestrial experiments, to a long-term dataset documenting phytoplankton communities in temperate coastal waters (Roscoff-ASTAN, France), combined with a public database of cell sizes. We compared the effects of the presence of pairs of species (“interactions”), size structure of the community, and abiotic effects on the autotrophic total biomass estimated by chlorophyll-a.

Including interactions in the statistical models improved the predictions of field-measured chlorophyll, and suggested that interactions reduced total chlorophyll by 24% on average. This pattern was consistent with expectations from intense, niche-based competition, as this negative effect decreased with differences in cell size. Interaction effects had smaller magnitudes than other model predictors, such as the number of cells and abiotic effects, but were remarkably stable throughout the yearly cycle.

These results show that while abiotic constraints are essential drivers of phytoplankton communities, interactions may largely modulate their productivity. This can be revealed using simple statistical models applied to observational data, which opens a way to a better understanding of the importance of interactions on ecosystem function in microbial systems at large temporal and spatial scales.

5.2. Introduction

5.2.1 Importance of biodiversity and interactions for functioning

Many ecosystem properties, such as productivity or community stability, are mediated by the number of species present in an ecosystem and the way these species interact. Negative interference between species, for example, may have detrimental effects on productivity, while synergistic effects like facilitation or mutualism may have beneficial effects (Loreau and Hector 2001). Identifying when and how these interactions drive ecosystem properties is essential to understand the consequences of species disappearance, a crucial question in the current context of rapid global changes.

While directly measuring interactions, in particular on microbial systems, is often tedious or downright impossible, we can evaluate their effects on ecosystem properties by comparing systems with different number of species. This is the cornerstone of biodiversity-ecosystem

functioning experiments, in which a set of species are cultivated together, and system-level properties like productivity are measured. In such an experiment, strong negative interference between species can be revealed by a lower productivity of the mixture of species. Conversely, facilitation, or a better collective use of environmental resources, would be revealed by a better performance of mixtures than isolated species. The latter is what appears to arise from more than two decades of terrestrial experiments: ecosystems containing more species tend to have higher productivity or stability (Tilman et al. (2001; Bell et al. 2005); but see Dee et al. (2023)), often due to a more efficient use of resources (Ptacnik et al. 2008; Ye et al. 2019)

Despite the great insights provided by these experimental approaches, they say little about naturally-assembled systems, for which the positive effects of biodiversity found in experiments often fail to replicate (Van Der Plas 2019; Duffy et al. 2017). Among such systems are phytoplankton communities, which are rarely amenable to experimental work, and seldom exhibit the positive biodiversity-productivity relationship found in experiments. Global datasets document increased productivities with species richness at the global scale, mediated by grazer abundance (Irigoiien et al. 2004; Vallina et al. 2014). However, this is not always found in data (Cermeño et al. 2013), and, remarkably, the most productive plankton systems can be found in algal blooms, which, in fact, contain very few species (Vallina et al. 2014; Spatharis et al. 2008).

This idiosyncrasy of biodiversity effects in observational data likely arises from the highly dynamic nature of phytoplankton communities (Goebel et al. 2013). While experiments start and develop in controlled conditions, natural phytoplankton communities are most often subject to stochastic effects that can blur or make biodiversity-ecosystem functioning relationships vanish (Thompson et al. 2021; Cermeño et al. 2013). Observational biases add another layer of complexity, as observational data are not always collected on the temporal or spatial scale at which the biological mechanisms operate, further affecting the observed relationships between species richness and productivity (Thompson et al. 2018). Taking into account these idiosyncrasies is required to evaluate how diversity and species interactions affect the productivity of these systems and what is their importance relative to abiotic factors.

5.2.2 Partitioning diversity effects on productivity in natural systems

Abiotic constraints on plankton productivity are well established. Nutrient and light limitations, for example, drive latitudinal and seasonal variation at the global scale (Margalef 1978; Benedetti et al. 2023). Yet, there is much room for biodiversity effects within these bounds. Synergistic effects between species can be present, whereby differences in physiological requirements of phytoplankton can lead to a more efficient use of resources overall. Phytoplankton groups segregate into different uptake strategies determined by a handful of functional traits, such as cell size or nutrient affinity (Edwards et al. 2012; Litchman et al. 2007). Theoretical and empirical work suggest that these functional differences lead to a more efficient use of resources and higher productivity, i.e. complementarity, (Ye et al. (2019; Vallina et al. 2017), but see Breton et al. (2017)). How

important this complementarity effect is relative to other factors in natura remains to be determined. Fortunately, new advances in data acquisition and analysis bring us closer to this goal.

While pelagic phytoplankton systems have been notoriously difficult to access and describe (Hays et al. 2005), decades of field collection efforts have produced datasets of large spatial and temporal extents, often spanning more than a decade, or with sampling campaigns performed at the global scale (Pierella Karlusich et al. 2020). This has developed in tandem with dramatic improvements in DNA-based taxonomic identification through metabarcoding (Abad et al. 2016; Andersson et al. 2023). These new amounts of data enable new, data-hungry statistical approaches to estimate the relevance of diversity effects to ecosystem functioning (e.g. Dee et al. (2023)), such as so-called Diversity-Interaction (DI) models (Kirwan et al. 2009).

DI models are a statistical framework designed to partition the contributions of biodiversity into environmental drivers, factors arising from species-specific effects, and pairwise effects capturing possible interactions between species (Kirwan et al. 2009; Connolly et al. 2011). This approach potentially overcomes a limitation of previous analyses, which often required cultivating individual species in isolation (“monocultures”) (Loreau and Hector 2001). Because DI models do not require monocultures to estimate biodiversity effects, they can be applied to natural contexts where the mixture of species are not fixed in advance by an experimental design, but naturally emerge from ecological dynamics. While this approach is not without limitations, we show here that it provides valuable insights to understand the underpinnings of productivity in phytoplankton systems, in particular to assess the relative role of abiotic constraints relative to endogenous factors such as species characteristics and interactions.

5.2.3 Study system

We showcase this approach using a public long-term dataset documenting the phytoplankton in coastal waters in the northern Atlantic (France, Caracciolo et al. (2022)). This dataset exemplifies a rising family of new, long-term plankton community datasets based on metabarcoding and environmental DNA (eDNA). We show how DI models can disentangle the many effects driving phytoplankton productivity, by linking the productivity of these systems, as measured through chlorophyll-a, to phytoplankton abundance, environmental conditions, as well as diversity components estimated by DI models, *i.e.* individual species contributions and interaction effects.

5.3. Methods

5.3.1 Community and environmental data

We used the public long-term dataset from the Somlit-ASTAN station (France), with samples collected bi-monthly between 2009 and 2016. Taxonomic data (Henry et al. 2021) were

obtained based on metabarcoding of the size fraction above 3 μm , which was purified, then amplified using primers of the V4 region of the 18S rRNA gene. Amplified reads were taxonomically-assigned using the PR2 database, then refined manually using BLAST, as per the protocol further described in Caracciolo et al. (2022). In addition to barcoding data, a public dataset with taxonomic assignments based on morphology was used (Rigaut-Jalabert et al. 2021), to derive an estimate of the total number of phytoplankton cells in each sample.

Taxonomic data from barcoding was aggregated at the genus level, *i.e.* we summed all reads assigned to a phytoplankton genus in a given sample, then rarefied all samples to 1000 reads (5 samples with a total number reads below 1000 were dropped, 2.6% of all observations).

Environmental data was obtained from the Somlit database (extracted on 2025-03-31, (Cocquempot et al. 2019)). On top of total chlorophyll a, we extracted ten environmental parameters: temperature, fluorescence, PAR, Salinity, concentrations of NO_2 , NO_3 , PO_4 , SiOH_4 and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, along with the concentration of bacteria (in cells/mL). Values were linearly interpolated to match the sampling dates of the taxonomic data.

5.3.2 Statistical modeling

We used a set of nested statistical models to disentangle and estimate the relative importance of biotic and non-biotic factors on the total chlorophyll measured in water. Calling μ_k the chlorophyll measured in a sample k , we first considered a constant model, whereby the average measured chlorophyll is considered to be always equal to a constant (an intercept):

$$\log(\mu_k) = \beta_0$$

We used the logarithm of chlorophyll instead of the raw value as it is non-negative. Extending this model, we then considered a mass effect model, whereby chlorophyll is tied to the number of phytoplankton cells found in a sample by a power relationship (Álvarez et al. 2017):

$$\log(\mu_k) = \beta_0 + \beta_m \log(C_k)$$

In this model, C_k is the total number of phytoplankton cells counted in a sample. This model assumes that the average chlorophyll found in a sample is directly and only related to the number of cells present in that sample.

Next, we expanded this model to include environmental covariates. We carried out a PCA on the environmental variables measured at each sample, and extracted the first two axes (Figure S5). These axes captured the main environmental variation throughout the year (explaining 51.1% of the variance). Using these two axes as covariates in the analyses

allowed taking into account broad environmental changes with a reduced number of variables, as following:

$$\log(\mu_k) = E_k = \beta_0 + \beta_m \log(C_k) + \beta_1 X_{1,k} + \beta_2 X_{2,k}$$

To add biodiversity effects to this base model E_k , we adopted the Diversity-Interaction modeling framework (Kirwan et al. 2009), which decomposes a property measured at the ecosystem level (here, total chlorophyll) into coefficients capturing contributions from individual species and pairs of species. In formal terms, this approach considers $\log(\mu_k)$ to be related to the total number of taxa present S and their relative proportions P_i for taxon i in sample k :

$$\log(\mu_k) = E_k + \sum_{i=1}^S \alpha_i P_{k,i} + \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i < j}}^S \delta_{ij} P_{k,i} P_{k,j}$$

The α_i s correspond to individual species contributions (i.e. what "amount" of chlorophyll each species brings in isolation). The double sum involving δ_{ij} s quantifies the added (or subtracted) ecosystem function resulting from having a pair of species present in a sample. A typical positive value for δ_{ij} indicates that the presence of these two species in a sample is beneficial for the ecosystem function, while a negative value means that the presence of these two species is detrimental.

5.3.3 Diversity-Interaction models and functional traits

The above DI models consider one coefficient per contribution of individual species (all α_i s) and pairs of species (δ_{ij} s), which is too many for species-rich contexts such as phytoplankton communities. We reduced the number of parameters by assuming that species identity and interaction effects were tied to functional traits. This is a reasonable assumption for phytoplankton communities, where vital rates (growth, nutrient acquisition) across species scale with a limited number of functional traits, such as cell size (Litchman et al. 2007; Aksnes and Egge 1991). This motivates the assumption that α_i is linearly related to cell size t_i as $\alpha_i = \alpha t_i$, and δ_{ij} is linearly related to the difference in cell size $t_i - t_j$ as $\delta_{ij} = \delta_0 + \delta \vee t_i - t_j \vee$. Substituting these assumptions into the previous equation yields the full DI model we used to partition productivity into its multiple components:

$$\log(\mu_k) = \beta_0 + \beta_m \log(C_k) + \beta_1 X_{1,k} + \beta_2 X_{2,k} + \sum_{i=1}^S \alpha t_i P_{k,i} + \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i < j}}^S (\delta_0 + \delta \vee t_i - t_j \vee) P_{k,i} P_{k,j}$$

This full model decomposes the ecosystem function into several components added to an intercept: *mass effects* based on cell counts, the *environmental effects*, the species-specific effects or *identity effects*, and *interaction effects*. By fitting the full model to data, we can test how these different components contribute to ecosystem function.

We obtained the cell sizes from a public dataset compiled from the literature by Harrison et al. (2015) from 40 long term coastal datasets similar in nature to the Roscoff-ASTAN dataset. For each genus, we computed the average reported equivalent spherical diameter (ESD) and used it as our trait measurement (t_i in the Equation of the full model), which is directly derived from cell volume as $ESD = 2\left(\frac{3V}{4\pi}\right)^{1/3}$. (Harrison 2015) reports ranges of diameters for each species, sometimes spanning orders of magnitude. To test the robustness of our results given this uncertainty, we repeated our analyses, starting with random cell sizes taken within the reported range.

We assumed that measurements of chlorophyll in samples followed a normal distribution around the log-transformed total chlorophyll in the sample, *i.e.* , $\log(y_k) \sim N(\mu_k, \sigma)$ with a constant parameter. Models were fitted in a Bayesian setting using wide, uninformative priors (uniform distributions between -100 and 100 for all coefficients).

5.3.4 Evaluating the importance and sign of interactions

We first evaluated the explanatory power of the different model components to predict the total chlorophyll present in a sample. To do so, we fitted models with an increasing number of terms, and compared their ability to predict empirical patterns. We first considered a constant, intercept-only model, with environmental effects (PCA scores), total cell count, and both. We then added to the latter model species identity effects, and then interaction effects. We compared the predictive ability of these six models using the Watanabe-Akaike Information Criterion (wAIC). Lower values of wAIC indicate that a model is able to better predict the observed chlorophyll values, taking into account its number of parameters.

We then estimated the magnitude of the contributions of environmental, mass, and diversity effects to chlorophyll in the field. We fitted the full model, then predicted, for each sample, the value of each model component (braces in the equation of the full model). This breaks down, for each observation of the dataset, the magnitude and sign of contributions of all model components to the total chlorophyll of that sample. For a given sample k , the contribution of species identity effects for a given sample k is given by the sum $\sum_{i=1}^S \alpha t_i P_{k,i}$ with $P_{k,i}$ the proportions of species i in sample k .

Finally, to estimate how complementarity effects varied with functional differences, we considered an artificial community of two species with equal abundances and a fixed distance in trait space d_0 . Under these assumptions, the contribution of interaction effects is proportional to $\delta_0 + \delta d_0$, which is a linear relationship that can be plotted. If pairwise processes captured by the DI model represent niche-based competition that reduces productivity, we expect species with similar trait values to be less beneficial or even

detrimental to productivity ($\delta_0 < 0$), and this pattern to decay with functional dissimilarity (*i.e.* to function than dissimilar species in trait space, or, in formal terms, *i.e.* we expect $\delta > 0$.

5.4. Results

5.4.1 No emergent diversity-function relationship

As is common with empirical biodiversity-ecosystem functioning relationships (Van Der Plas 2019), we did not find an increasing relationship of total chlorophyll with the richness of the phytoplankton community (number of genera, Figure 5.1). Instead, we found a non-significant, slightly negative power relationship, with a non-significant exponent of -0.50 (95% confidence interval of [-1.21, 0.22]).

Figure 5.1. Diversity (number of genera) - productivity (chl_a) relationship for the Astan dataset. The trend line indicates the best fit of a power relationship of the form .

5.4.2 Interaction effects are needed to predict function

We found that models including species contributions and interactions provided a better prediction of ecosystem functioning, as evidenced by the generally lower wAIC of models that included these components (Figure 5.2). The best predictive ability was achieved by including all components, with a difference of 11.3 with the next best model (more than five times the common cutoff of two for statistical significance). This full model captured the

overall distribution of the data (supplementary figure 5.4a), and showed no residual autocorrelation at a time scale of one year (supplementary figure 5.4c), indicating that it captured the variability along the seasonal cycle. The model did exhibit some temporal autocorrelation in residuals at a lag of four observations (60 days; supplementary figure 5.4c). Coefficient estimates were relatively robust to uncertainty in trait data, even though some coefficients had 95 % credible intervals overlapping zero once this uncertainty was factored in (Table 1, Supplementary Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2. Models wAIC depending on the components included in the model for the Roscoff ASTAN dataset.

5.4.3 Species interactions appear detrimental to productivity

Turning to the contributions of individual components to chlorophyll, we found that cell count contributed a large part of total chlorophyll, increasing the log-transformed chlorophyll by 2.2 (95% credible interval of [1.9, 2.8], Figure 5.3a). Other components had a lower contribution, with species identity effects increasing the log-transformed chlorophyll by 0.33 ([0.14, 0.61]), and interaction effects decreasing it by -0.28 ([-0.45, -0.05], Figure 3b). The contribution of

environmental effects was estimated at zero (95% interval of [-0.32, 0.39]), but a breakdown by month revealed that these effects were positive from May to September, and negative from October to April (Figure 5.3c). All other components had comparatively lower variation throughout the year, although identity effects were overall slightly higher in spring and summer months (Figure 5.3c).

Figure 5.3. Contributions of each model component for all samples (a and b), and broken down by month (c). Values above zero indicate a positive effect of this component on total chlorophyll a, with each observation corresponding to a sample in the dataset. Note the change in scale for the cell count effects in panel (a), breakdown by month for the effect of cell count is given in Supplementary Figure 1.

Table 5.1 (below). Estimated model coefficients, and bounds of 95% credible intervals (C.I.) using the best trait estimate, as well as expanded bounds after resampling trait values from the original dataset (see also Supplementary Figure 5.2). Note that the magnitudes of coefficients do not necessarily indicate larger effects on total chlorophyll for a given variable.

Coef.	Interpretation	Average estimate	95% C.I.	95 % C.I. (resampled trait values)
	Effect of cell count	0.23	[0.17, 0.29]	-
	Effect of environment (PCA Axis 1)	-0.38	[-0.49, -0.27]	-
	Effect of environment (PCA Axis 2)	0.19	[0.08, 0.30]	-
	Cell size effect	0.02	[0.01, 0.02]	[-0.00, 0.02]

Contribution for species with similar size	-2.15	[-3.32, -0.98]	[-3.02, 0.18]
Change in contribution with difference in cell size	0.07	[0.03, 0.12]	[-0.04, 0.09]
Model intercept	-2.57	[-3.29, -1.87]	-
Model residual error	0.33	[0.30, 0.37]	-

5.4.4 Interaction effects depend on size differences

Using simulations based on the fitted model, we found that the contribution of pairs of species varied with the distance in trait space. The contribution of two species with identical cell size was significantly negative (estimated of -2.02, with 95% credible interval of [-3.12, -0.87]; 1), but increased with the difference in size, as was estimated positive at 0.07 (95% credible interval of [0.03, 0.11]). These parameter estimates corresponded to a negative contribution to productivity of species pairs with identical cell sizes, which increased to zero at a size difference of approximately 30 μm (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4. Interaction component in the case of a two-species community with fixed functional distance and equal proportions. Values above (below) 0 indicate positive (negative) contributions to productivity. Ribbons indicate the 95% credible intervals, the

interquartile range (darker shade), and the line corresponds to the median posterior estimate. Ticks on the x-axis indicate the distances found in empirical data.

5.5 Discussion

A major challenge of ecology is determining when and how diversity and species interactions matter for ecosystem functioning and services on natural systems. We presented and used an approach with great potential for application to different contexts to tackle this challenge. We applied a statistical model to a phytoplankton time-series that exemplifies the data types that modern sampling technologies offer. Our Diversity-Interaction model suggested that total field-measured chlorophyll was driven by more than just cell abundance and environmental factors, since cell size and pairwise effects improved model predictions and had notable magnitudes. Samples with larger taxa contributed larger amounts of chlorophyll, and pairwise effects between species appeared detrimental to productivity, suggesting intense competition in the phytoplankton community. These negative effects appeared consistent with niche-based mechanisms, as they vanished with increasing size differences between taxa.

While negative pairwise effects were remarkably constant throughout the year, other effects were more variable, and overall in agreement with well-known phytoplankton seasonal cycles observed in this region. The environmental effects on productivity turned from negative in the winter months to positive in spring, matching the change of light limitation between these seasons (Edwards et al. 2013). The slight increase in the effect of cell size from winter to summer is also consistent with the early development of small, fast-reproducing taxa (Caracciolo et al. 2022), followed by a shift towards larger taxa as heterotroph grazing increases (Grattepanche et al. 2011; Acevedo-Trejos et al. 2015). Given this highly dynamical seasonal cycle, the stability of pairwise negative effects is remarkable, suggesting that despite large changes in taxonomic and functional composition, the effects of niche-based competition remained temporally stable.

Despite little apparent relationship between diversity and productivity (Figure 5.1), DI models revealed a significant effect of mechanisms involving species interactions, highlighting the ability of this approach to identify the effects of potential interactions despite large natural variability. Interestingly, the model we used (full model equation) has much in common with the use of taxonomic and functional diversity indices. The interaction effects can be expressed as the sum of a taxonomic and a functional diversity index. This makes our simple model above directly related to the work using functional indices as predictors of productivity (e.g. Breton et al. (2017; Ye et al. 2019)). However, an approach based on DI models can be extended to disentangle pairwise relationships beyond a simple metric characterizing the community as a whole, using random (Brophy et al. 2017) or non-linear effects (Connolly et al. 2013).

Although our simple linear model could explain a large fraction of empirical patterns, and was overall a good fit to the data (supplementary figure 5.4a), some insightful minor

deviations remained. Perhaps the most revealing one is the positive temporal autocorrelation in residuals up to a lag of 4 observations (60 days). This highlights the presence of unexplained inertia in ecological dynamics, in which the chlorophyll measured at a given time is partially influenced by previous weeks. This matches previous analyses of the same dataset (Caracciolo et al. 2022), and does not appear to be explained by factors within the phytoplankton community. A likely explanation is the development of the grazer community, as this time lag is on the same order of magnitude as the generation time of zooplankton (Barton et al. 2020). Testing this hypothesis could be done by including a proxy of grazing pressure in the model, if data are available, whose inclusion should reduce temporal autocorrelation in the residuals.

Another insightful deviation are the very low amounts of observed chlorophyll, which are not predicted by the model (supplementary figure 5.4b). While fluorescence-measured chlorophyll content is a widespread and practical proxy of autotrophic biomass, its values can deviate in some cases (Álvarez et al. 2017; Huot et al. 2007). This can arise if cells have lower pigment concentrations as a result of e.g. light limitation which could be the mechanism here as most of the deviating samples correspond to winter conditions. This highlights the core assumptions of using a statistical model, which equates both sides of an equation and assuming they measure the same thing (here, plankton biomass), while this may not always be true in practice when using proxy variables. Again, non-linear transformations of variables, or inclusion of extra covariates could help take into account such factors.

Our study exemplifies the potential of DI models to compare ecosystems and predict emerging ecosystem properties and the relative roles of the environment, trait distributions and biotic interactions. We focused on a single dataset of relatively cold and nutrient-rich waters, but phytoplankton communities at lower latitudes or with stronger water stratification would most likely show different patterns. In nutrient-poor waters, synergistic relationships emerging from nitrogen-fixation may play a larger role, which could be reflected in positive contributions of the interaction component of a DI model (Gérikas Ribeiro et al. 2018; Montoya et al. 2004). This pattern would mirror what is observed in terrestrial plant systems, which often show strong competition in benign conditions that transitions to facilitation in abiotically stressed environments that produce higher total biomass, a phenomenon coined as the Stress Gradient Hypothesis, which has received support in experimental microbial systems (Piccardi et al. 2019).

The application of DI models to other datasets, in particular time-series, hinges on reducing the large diversity of forms of microbes onto a few dimensions based on functional traits. The availability of these traits is key, and global databases are instrumental to compare patterns across ecosystems. Coordinated efforts to curate and make these data available have been done for other groups (e.g. terrestrial plants, Kattge et al. (2020)), but have yet to emerge for many taxonomic groups of microbes. Applying DI models to new observations and trait datasets is likely to help better identify the limits and promises of the approach, when applied to natural systems.

5.6. Additional material

Supplementary Figure 5.1. PCA of environmental variables. Each point represents a sample, with the size and color representing the total chlorophyll a. 'tbacc' stands for the number of bacteria in the sample (cells/mL), 'salin' is the salinity of the sample, 'temp' the temperature, 'fluo' the fluorescence (unknown unit), 'par' the Photosynthetically Active Radiation ($\mu\text{E}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), 'dn15' the ().

Supplementary Figure 5.2. Contribution of the *mass effect* component (cell count) broken down by month. Values above 0 (horizontal bar) indicate larger contributions of this

component to the total chlorophyll in water. Ribbon indicate the 95% interval of individual values for each month.

Supplementary Figure 5.3. Posterior density estimates for each model parameter using the best (median) cell size reported for each taxon (red), and combined posterior densities after 39 resamples of the original trait data, each time sampling one trait value per species illustrative of the reported range (blue). The meaning of model parameters is given in Table 1.

Supplementary Figure 5.4. Diagnostics for the full statistical model (Equation [eq:full_model]). (a) Empirical density of observations (black), and 100 densities of predicted observations from the posterior predictive distribution. A good fit is attained if all densities have similar shapes. (b) Predicted vs. Observed values of total chlorophyll (log-transformed). A good fit implies that 95% of observations fall homogeneously between the dotted line. (c) Autocorrelation of residuals (observed minus predicted average chlorophyll for observations). Modelling assumes no residual autocorrelation, *i.e.* the ribbon intersects the 0-line. The vertical line indicates a lag of 24 samples, *i.e.* a year of sampling.

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